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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT

OF THE

ARCHAEOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT

GWALIOR STATE

FOR

VIKRAM SAMVAT 1997, YEAR 1940-41.

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1943

ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT

ARCHAEOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT

GWALIOR STATE

FOR THE YEAR 1957-58

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT

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ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT, GWALIOR STATE

FOR THE

Year Ending 30th June 1941, Samvat 1997.

Charge.—The undersigned held charge of the Department throughout the year under report.

2. *Leave.*—Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows :—

(a) *Inspector.*—Thirty-four days' privilege leave from the 16th to the 24th December 1940 and from the 6th to the 30th June 1941.

(b) *General Assistant.*—Eleven days' privilege leave from the 3rd to the 13th July 1940.

(c) *Assistant Photographer—Draughtsman.*—Privilege leave for 13 days from the 18th to the 30th April 1941.

3. *Administrative Changes.*—None.

4. *Promotions.*—On the auspicious occasion of His Highness' marriage, *tofir* of Rs. 10 in the monthly salary of Mr. G. M. Nadkarni, the Inspector, and *tofir* of Rs. 5 p. m. in the salary of Mr. Ram Prasad Varma, the permanent *mistri*, were released with effect from the 21st of February 1941.

5. *Rewards.*—On the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Birthday the Darbar were pleased to confer a gold watch on Mr. S. K. Dikshit, M. A., New Delhi, who rendered honorary services to the Archæological Department during the archæological excavations which were carried out at Ujjain, in Samvat 1995, year 193 -39.

6. *General.*—All the office staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, diligently and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

II. Circulars and Departmental Orders.

7. No Circular or Departmental Order with special reference to this Department was issued in the year of report.

III. Work at Headquarters.

8. In addition to the ordinary office routine, the following work was done during the headquarters season :—

(a) The Annual Administration Report for Samvat 1996 (year 1939-40) was drawn up and submitted along with an

album of select photographs of monuments and antiquities, etc., taken in the year under report.

- (b) The Annual Administration Report for Samvat 1995 (year 1938-39) was printed and published and the Annual Administration Report for Samvat 1996 was sent to the Press for printing.
- (c) The Budget estimate for Samvat 1998 was drawn up and submitted.
- (d) Repairs were carried out to improve the building of the Gujar Mahal where the Archæological Museum is housed.
- (e) Rubbish and debris were partially cleared up in order to expose the interesting buildings which lay half-concealed in earth at the back of the Gujar Mahal.
- (f) A programme of conservation work for the next season was drawn up and relative estimates prepared.
- (g) Antiquities unearthed in excavations at Pawaya (District Gird), and at Ujjain, were cleaned, studied, listed and photographed, and important specimens were selected for exhibition at the Museum.
- (h) Inscriptions discovered in the year were deciphered and studied.
- (i) Coins received as treasure-trove finds, or as offers for purchase or exchange, as well as those found in excavations, were examined.
- (j) A list of duplicate coins available for sale or exchange in the Archæological Department was printed and circulated among the Museums in India, and the orders received for supply of coins were attended to.
- (k) Paintings, terra cotta and metal images received for inspection and approval were examined, and such as were found suitable were purchased for the Archæological Museum.
- (l) Antiquities acquired for the Museum were properly exhibited. Enamel labels were prepared for a number of sculptural exhibits in the Museum.
- (m) The copies of the Bagh Paintings in the Museum were re-arranged.
- (n) Twenty-seven half-tone blocks for illustrating the Annual Administration Report for Samvat 1996, and six half-tone blocks relating to Picture Postcards of Bagh Caves were prepared and printed.
- (o) A note on Archæology and Antiquities was contributed for the Revised Edition of the Commercial and General

Directory of Gwalior State being published by the Department of Commerce and Industries.

- (p) Proofs of articles on the Tumain Inscription of Kumargupta and Ghatotkachagupta and the Mandasor Inscription of Govindagupta and Prabhakara contributed to the *Epigraphia Indica* were revised and returned.
- (q) Photographic Negatives were printed and Drawings faded out.
- (r) Enlarged photographs of certain Archæological Monuments were supplied to the Publicity Officer, Gwalior Government.
- (s) Some photographs of Moslem Monuments were supplied to the Aukaph Department.
- (t) Arranged a stall of Archæological exhibits as a part of the Art Exhibition on the Mela Grounds.
- (u) Various queries from scholars were answered and information, photographs and publications, etc., were supplied to them, on request.
- (v) Distinguished visitors were shown round the Archæological Museum and monuments on the Gwalior Fort.

IV. Tours.

9. During the year of report the Director spent 102 days in camp, including four days' special tour outside the Gwalior State, for the annual inspection of conserved and maintained monuments, for directing and supervising works of conservation and excavation, for preparing estimates of work to be undertaken next year, and for exploring ancient monuments and prospective sites for archæological excavations. A detailed Tour Diary is given in Appendix A.

10. Visits of annual inspection were paid to conserved monuments at Besnagar, Bhilsa, Gyaspur, Kakpur and Udaypur (District Bhilsa), Dhumeswar (District Gird), Chanderi (District Guna), Mandasor (District Mandasor), Padhavli (District Morena), Mahua, Surwaya and Terahi (District Shivpuri).

11. Udaygiri (District Bhilsa), Antri and Gwalior (District Gird), Kadwaha (District Guna), Khor and Sondni (District Mandasor), Badegaon and Suhania (District Morena), Bagh and Jamli (District Sardarpur), and Chorpura (District Shivpuri) were visited for directing and inspecting conservation works.

12. Makhanganj (District Mandasor) and Mitaoli (District Morena) were inspected for drawing up estimates for conservation works proposed to be done.

13. Amrol (District Gird), Baredi, Kutwar, Paytha and Samantukhera (District Morena) and Dadur (District Sardarpur) were

explored for ancient monuments and prospective sites for archæological excavations. While Pawaya (District Gird) and Ujjain were visited more than once for directing excavation works.

14. Barai and Panihar (District Gird) were visited in connection with a request made by some Jain leaders from outside the State, to be allowed to take away a big Jain idol from the ruins of an old temple at Barai. The Aukaph Department called for the opinion of this Department in this matter and was informed in reply that it was advisable to repair the temple and to preserve the idol in its original place.

15. In the course of special tours outside the State which the Director made with the special permission of Hon'ble the Home Minister, he visited Ramnagar and New Delhi with a view to study the latest methods of archæological excavations and of recording, preserving and studying antiquities unearthed.

V. Conservation.

(i) Initial Repairs to Ancient Monuments.

16. In the year under report, the Government's liberal policy in the provision of necessary funds for (the nation-building and) cultural work, enabled this Department to pursue with unabated vigour its activities in the field of conservation. The fourth instalment of Rupees ten thousand (10,000) for further conservation of the Bagh Caves, our premier monument, and Rupees one thousand and five hundred (1,500) for improving Gujari Mahal Building, or Rupees eleven thousand and five hundred (11,500) in all, were sanctioned as non-recurring special grants to supplement the limited recurring grant for works in the regular budget. Savings from the 'ast year's grants were also utilised with the sanction of the Finance Department.

17. Conservation works were carried out at Udaygiri (District Bhilsa), Antri and Gwalior (District Gird), Chanderi and Kadwaha (District Guna), Khor and Sondni (District Mandasor), Suhania (District Morena), Bagh and Jamli (District Sardarpur), and Chorapura (District Shivpuri), at a total cost of Rs. 14,661-14-2.

18. A statement of conservation works and the expenditure incurred on them appears in Appendix B.

(District Bhilsa.)

19. *Udaygiri*.—The ground in front of Caves Nos. 16 and 17 was irregular and presented an ugly appearance. It had been improved to some extent in previous years. The final touches were given in the year of report.

(1) Platforms of earthwork with level tops and with sides held by retaining walls of masonry in stone were constructed in front of both the caves. Masonry steps were provided to get up to the platforms. The surrounding ground was levelled up or sloped regularly according to local exigencies.

(2) The *pucca* edging of the drain between the road and the frontage of caves was further extended for a length of about 40 feet from Cave No. 7. up to Cave No 16.

- (3) In order to improve the passage which leads from Cave No. 19, up the hill to Cave No. 20 and the Rest House, a mound of earth mixed with boulders near Cave No. 19, was dug up and an adjoining depression was filled up.
- (4) And the *kachcha* steps at the foot of the hill were strengthened with large stone slabs planted on edge in front and with lines of stone uprights, at the sides.

(District Gird Gwalior.)

20. *Antri*.—The tomb believed to be that of Abul Fazal, the learned author of the *Ain-i-Akbari* and the favourite counsellor of Akbar, had already been conserved. But it was in need of further attention. The following repairs were carried out here in the year of report :—

- (1) The bulging portions of the platform on which the tomb is set were dismantled and properly re-built.
- (2) Alignments of the parapet walls on the north, east and south sides of the platform were not in straight lines. The lime *gola* which capped the retaining walls had been badly damaged by village children using it as a seat. All the three lines of the parapet wall 38, 29 and 38 feet in length, respectively, were therefore dismantled and re-built on a straight line plan. In the reconstruction stone slab coping was substituted for the lime *gola* on these walls with a view to avoid continual damage and necessity of recurring repairs. The wall on the west was only repaired in patches and the lime *gola* on it was restored instead of being replaced with slab coping, as the top of the wall was too high to be reached and damaged by children.
- (3) The passage in the north side was closed up and the steps removed.
- (4) The passage in the east side was protected with wooden bars inserted in stone uprights for preventing cattle climbing up and damaging the platform.
- (5) The tile *jalis* in windows were repaired.
- (6) The cracks in walls of the room were closed up.
- (7) The terrace floor of the room was repaired with a coat of lime, polished with cement.
- (8) The top of the platform was levelled by cutting and filling.
- (9) The outer faces of the platform and both the faces of the parapet walls were treated with cut lime pointing, and the whole monument was re-white-washed.
- (10) *Bajri* was spread on the top of the platform and the surrounding area demarcated with the boundary posts.

21. *Gwalior*.—For the general improvement of the Gujari Mahal building which is itself a precious Archæological Monument and in which the Archæological Museum is also housed, various items of repairs, additions and alterations consistent (of course) with the original plan and design of the edifice were carried out, the more important of which are :—

- (1) A 3" thick stone coping with chamfered edges was provided on the top of the low parapet wall which enclosed the central square courtyard. Besides improving the look of the courtyard it serves as lines of seats for tired visitors to take rest.
- (2) Sinks were constructed at the four corners of the coping, to do duty as flower beds.
- (3) The terrace floor of the open yard in front of Room No. 3 and Rooms Nos. 6 to 10, which seems to have been put in during repairs, at a later date, after the Mahal had fallen into neglect and disrepair, had got damaged. It was therefore dug up with a view to repair and level it up with a new coat of lime concrete and polish, so as to make it stronger, neater and tidier in appearance. During the digging operations, the original plan of western portion of the building consisting of small courtyards alternating with rooms, walls and drains, which lay concealed under the later terrace floor, was revealed. In one place, a pit or cellar enclosed with walls of rough stone masonry came to light. The cellar is 18' north to south and 7' east to west and is divided into two parts by a partition wall 4' thick pierced with an opening. What this pit was intended for, is not quite clear. It may have been a soak pit. Similar cellars exist elsewhere in the courtyard, *e. g.*, one between Rooms Nos. 3 and 4 and another between Rooms Nos. 5 and 6.

The courtyards recently brought to light, sink a few inches below the floors of the rooms and are lined with *dasa* decorated with leaf design.

The whole terrace floor thus dug up was repaired with a coat of lime concrete. In repairing it, however, care has been taken to follow and retain the original plan exposed to view. The cellar being of no archæological interest was covered up again. Suitable drainage was provided joining the new drains with the old ones.

- (4) A six feet wide strip in the terrace floor which was used as a footpath by visitors for communicating with Rooms Nos. 6 to 11 and which got repeatedly damaged by being trampled, was paved with stone slabs so as to make a durable passage.
- (5) The pedestals of the *Chakravyuha* and the amphitheatre were remodelled substituting stone slabs on edge for the lime plaster on faces.

- (6) Tree guards of brick were constructed for protection of the three mango trees newly planted in the premises, on the east of the Mahal.

22. Another piece of conservation work was taken in hand in connection with the Gujari Mahal. At the back, *i. e.*, on the north of the palace, a spacious hall facing north flanked by a side room at each end and designed and massively built like the palace itself, was partially visible, being half buried in debris and silt. It appeared to be an annexe or an extension of the palace proper. In order to investigate this point, the work of clearing up debris and rubbish from the hall and its surroundings was commenced late in June. Little progress was made by the close of the year. Only the plan of a courtyard with two side wings was partially exposed.

23. In the bank of ground between the hall and the well situated outside the N. W. corner of the Gujari Mahal, an opening looking like the mouth of an underground passage was partially visible. When it was freed from debris it proved to be the mouth of huge pucca drain 4 to 5 feet wide and about 8 feet deep, flanked on both sides by strong retaining walls of stone masonry and spanned with stone slabs carried on lintels. It extends over about 123 feet in length north to south inside the foundations of the palace. The work will be resumed next year, when discoveries of interesting buildings are expected.

(District Guna.)

24. *Chanderi* —The horses' tomb adjoining the footpath leading to the Paramesvara Tal had become dilapidated. The masonry of the platform supporting the two statues of horses had fallen in several places. The statues of horses were leaning out of position. The whole platform was therefore dismantled and re-built with old stone after the original design. The top of the platform was paved partly with new stones. The horses' statues were properly re-set.

25. *Kadwaha*.—The work of partial conservation of the mediæval Hindu monastery and temples at Kadwaha had been commenced but left unfinished last year (see Annual Report for V. S. 1996, *paras* Nos. 20 to 23).

26. The remaining items of the proposed work were done in the year of report, thus :—

- (1) The room on the third storey over the staircase of the monastery was dismantled and completely re-built, with the exception of the roof.
- (2) Cut stone masonry pillars were constructed to support certain huge stone beams (two on the ground floor and one on the first floor) which had cracked and sagged and which had been supported on temporary piles of stones.
- (3) A flight of steps 10 feet wide, was constructed for giving access to the floor of the *Garhi* which is about 12 feet

lower than the level of the approach road. The steps are of rubble stone masonry with treaders of stone slabs. The entrance to the steps is through a pair of cut stone posts, which is guarded temporarily with a rough wooden gate against cattle trespassing into the *Garhi*.

- (4) A *pucca* drain is constructed for the outlet of rain water from the *Garhi*.
- (5) A huge ceiling slab of stone was lying unevenly near temple No. 4. It was re-set level and supported on low masonry pillars so as to make the slab serve as a seat for visitors to rest on.
- (6) The whole structure of temple No. 7 (*Marghatte-ki-Marhi*) has been badly disturbed and gone out of plumb. To restore it to its right (original) position is impossible unless the whole is dismantled and re-built, which is a prohibitively expensive proposition. We had therefore to be content with doing what was reasonably possible, in order to make the temple safe and tidy looking. A pillar of the porch which had badly tilted out was re-set upright after jacking up the super-structure. The masonry of the basement of the temple and porch was repaired by underpinning with cut stone blocks.
- (7) The banks of earthwork with which the damaged plinths of temples had been covered up last year were dressed up into regular slopes.
- (8) The ground around the conserved temples was levelled as far as possible, and cleaned up. The premises of temples Nos. 1 and 2 were demarcated with cut stone boundary posts planted at the four corners.

27. Although the work included in the first estimate has thus been done, the work of conservation of the monastery and some of the temples is by no means complete. In fact, more work than what has been carried out still, awaits being done. This remaining work will have to be done perhaps in more than one instalments in the near future, when funds become available.

(District Mandasor.)

28. *Khor*.—The Nau Toran temple on the road side in front of the village *Khor* had been already conserved. It was further improved in the year of report when the following items of work were executed:—

- (1) A lunatic had displaced a few blocks of stone two or three years ago. They were properly re-set.
- (2) The pavement of the shrine room was repaired.

- (3) The iron bands used for supporting, by way of conservation, the stone arches which had cracked, were re-painted to match with the colour of old stone, and the fissures between the stone arches and the bands were closed up with cement mortar.
- (4) The loose carved stones found in excavations in the premises of the temple were re-arranged around the temple so as to make the premises look neat and tidy.
- (5) The premises were levelled up by cutting and filling ups and downs.

29. The large ruined platform of another temple which is no longer standing is locally known as *Bhamvra* owing to a small cellar in the north-west corner of the platform. These ruins were partially conserved this year.

- (1) Jungle was cleared 25 feet all round.
- (2) Portions of the platform which lay buried in debris consisting of earth mixed with heavy stone were exposed down to the original ground level by excavating and throwing away debris.
- (3) The heavy carved stones found in the debris were collected in one place.
- (4) The cellar was freed from debris.
- (5) The upper courses of the eastern wall of the cellar were repaired in cut stone.
- (6) Broken lintels and ceiling slabs of the cellar were replaced. Only old stones found on the site have been used in the repairs.

30. A third monument at Khor attended to in the year of report is the remnant of a temple on the road side in the fifth mile of the Jawad-Kesarpura road, near the ruins of an old well locally known as Bilya Baodi. What now survives of the original temple is an oblong room facing the west, with its back towards the road. The back wall of the temple is lined with niches originally sheltering images of Hindu gods, now all but one vacant. One of the niches is inset with a standing image of Vishnu. The temple is far advanced in ruin. The walls which are made up of large blocks of stone without mortar are badly shaken. The roof is now flat but originally it may have been crowned with a spire or spires.

- (1) The ruins of the temples were freed from jungle.
- (2) The high ground on which the temple stands sloped irregularly on all sides and this presented an unsightly appearance. To make the premises neat and tidy, a platform of earthwork with a level top and regularly sloping banks was laid round the basement of the temple.

- (3) A few stones of the walls which had badly moved out of position were re-set.

(District Morena.)

31. *Suhania*.—The old well near the famous Kakanmadh temple had been excavated last year to a depth of 59 feet and patch repairs had been executed to the surviving old masonry of the well.

- (1) In the year of report, the well was further excavated to a total depth of 80 feet, the original depth of the well.
- (2) The upper courses of the original wall masonry of the well had fallen in. They were restored with new masonry so as to raise the circular enclosure wall to a height of 3 feet above the surrounding ground level. A *pucca ghat* with the arrangement for drawing water still remains to be constructed. The work will be done as soon as funds permit.
- (3) The gaps in the compound wall of the temple area caused by the removal of some stones for use in the repair to the well, were made good.

(District Sardarpur.)

32. *Bagh*.—The only major work of conservation carried out in the year of report was that at Bagh Caves. This work was pushed forward with the fourth instalment of Rupees ten thousand (10,000) sanctioned in the year of report.

33. Cave No. 2.—(1) Pillar No. 10 in the back row in the hall of this cave which had disappeared altogether was restored after the design of the corresponding pillar on the other side. As in the restoration of other pillars, the repairs consisted of cut stone casing finely dressed, and hearting of cement concrete. With the construction of this pillar the hall is now complete with all its pillars.

(2) Pillars Nos. 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, 11, 14 and 17 of the hall and the two pillars of the vestibule had suffered damage and had been repaired by the mediæval dwellers with mud. The mud was therefore scraped off and the damaged portions were repaired with cement concrete with re-inforcement where necessary.

(3) The *dasa* of the vestibule and sills of a few cells were repaired with cut stone.

34. Cave No. 3.—(1) A tamarind tree dangerously growing on the hill side just over the N. W. corner of the left wing of the cave was rooted out and the crevices caused by the roots of the tree were grouted with cement.

(2) A large fissure about three feet high and two feet deep caused by the decay of rock and running along the whole facade of the cave from end to end was filled up with cement

concrete in order to unite the ceiling of the cave with the living rock above, and thus strengthening the facade of the cave.

(3) Some crevices in the ceiling of the cave were repaired with cement concrete and cement *bajri*.

(4) The pillars of the verandah of the inner suite of cells on the left side were repaired with re-inforced cement concrete.

(5) Portions in the walls of the line of cells on the right side were repaired with cut stone in lime after cutting out the decayed rock.

35. Cave No. 4.—(1) Pillar No. 28 at the S. W. corner of the hall was completely restored with cut stone facing and cement concrete hearting, after the decayed portion of the surviving rock had been chiselled out. The gap between the top of the regular pillar and the existing ceiling caused by the dropping away of the rock was filled up with hammer dressed stone masonry in cement.

(2) Shallow depressions and fissures in the walls of the verandahs, caused by the decay of rock, were repaired with cement concrete.

(3) The rock floor of the left verandah which had been badly damaged owing to the decay of rock and had become rather dangerous for the feet of visitors was levelled up partly by chiselling off the ups in the rock and then laying a coat of cement concrete all over the floor.

36. Cave No. 5.—By far the major portion of the repair work at Bagh Caves for this year was done in Cave No. 5. This cave consists of a large oblong hall 95 feet long and 44 feet wide. The ceiling was supported on two rows of eight pillars each. All but three of these pillars had disappeared almost completely and the whole ceiling was overhanging on precarious support. The walls, and the door and window openings of this cave have also badly suffered from the decay of the rock. This cave is important for its unusual plan and the peculiar design of its pillars, which consisted of circular shafts slightly tapering upwards with round *golas* at the top.

37. The repairs to this cave executed in the year of report comprise the following :—

(1) Pillars Nos. 1 to 4 in the front row which had either badly decayed or had disappeared altogether were completely restored with cut stone plain and moulded work.

(2) Decayed portions of pillars Nos. 5, 6 and 8 were chiselled out and then they were restored with cement concrete with reinforcement where necessary.

- (3) Pillars Nos. 9 and 12 in the back row were restored completely and pillar No. 15 partially.
- (4) In the original design of the cave a continuous rock cut beam had been provided over the tops of pillars in each row. These beams had disappeared with the exception of the right half of the beam on the front row. After the restoration of all the pillars under the left half of the beam on the front row, the missing portion of the beam was restored in re-inforced cement concrete with a double line of steel girders in the hearting for the whole length, locating joints over the tops of pillars.
- (5) The gap between the re-inforced cement concrete beam and the existing ceiling representing the *rock* which has dropped away was filled up with stone in cement masonry.
- (6) Some cracks in the front portions of ceiling which could be reached conveniently from the scaffolding erected for the construction of the R. C. C. beam were filled up with cement concrete.
- (7) The decayed portions in the jambs and sills of the door and the windows were cut out and restored with cut stone blocks, backed with hammer dressed stone masonry where possible and necessary in order to reduce cost without sacrifice of strength or appearance. The original design of recesses has been faithfully copied in the restoration.
- (8) The decayed portions of the *dasa* joining the bases of pillars were restored with cut stone in cement.
- (9) The decayed base of the pilaster at the S. W. end of the common verandah of Caves Nos. 4 and 5 and the decayed portions of the walls and door of the adjacent cell were chiselled off and repaired with cut stone underpinning. The outer face of the right wall of the cell was repaired with hammer-dressed stone masonry, in order to match with original face of the wall.

38. *General.*—

- (1) Portion of the passage between Caves Nos. 3 and 4 was widened by cutting, breaking and throwing away blocks of rocks.
- (2) The stone platform constructed in previous years for the protection of the trees on the bank of the river in front of the caves was further extended.

Mural Paintings on the Bagh Caves.

39. Hand in hand with the conservation of the architectural relics of the Bagh Caves, their surviving mural paintings, the most precious feature for which they are known to the artistic world, have

been receiving the Department's attention. The wall paintings on the facade of Caves Nos. 4 and 5 were partially conserved some years ago. The ruined edges of the plaster were filled and the patches where plaster had peeled off were filled with a suitable composition of plaster of paris, cement and fine sand, coloured to match the original plaster. In the year of report, the Archæological Chemist in India—Khan Bahadur Sana Ullah, M. Sc.,—was invited to examine the paintings, to advise and demonstrate on the spot appropriate measures of the further conservation and cleaning of these paintings as well as of those on the interior of Caves Nos. 3 and 4. Mr. Shavrikar, the Draughtsman Artist of this Department, was deputed to learn and practise the work of conservation under the direct supervision of the Archæological Chemist who spent a few days at the caves in November 1940. The Archæological Chemist has prescribed the composition of the cementing material to be used for further repairs to the damaged plaster and has supplied the chemical solution to be used for cleaning the paintings. Mr. Shavrikar has picked up the work and the Archæological Chemist was satisfied with Mr. Shavrikar's work done under his supervision. The conservation and cleaning of the paintings will be pushed forward in the coming years as much as funds will permit. The Archæological Chemist recommends the employment of additional trained hands for expediting work as soon as possible, as the condition of the paintings is gradually deteriorating and it is advisable to treat them as soon as possible.

40. The problem of freeing the paintings which have been very badly obliterated from the thick coat of black soot, if possible, was also referred to the Archæological Chemist. He made a few experiments on the spot and came to the conclusion that it was not possible for chemistry in the present stage of its development to accomplish the desired task.

41. Another problem relating to the obscured paintings that of photographing them, if possible, with some special process such as photography with infra red plates, is also engaging our attention. At the instance of the Director-General of Archæology in India, some experiments were made by Mr. Joglekar, the Photographer of the Poona Office of the Archæological Survey of India, on some specimens sent to him. But it appears, that experiments on a large scale will have to be made on the spot, before it can be definitely decided whether photography can succeed in reclaiming the paintings.

42. The required material such as special plates being not easily available during war time, the experimentation has to be postponed till after the World War.

43. *Jamli*.—The Mahadeva temple near Jamli, a village situated about 12 miles to the east of Tanda, which dates back to the 10th or 11th century A. D., is the only specimen of mediæval temple architecture which has survived almost entirely in this tract of country. The Mahakal temple at Bagh is another bigger temple of

the same age, but it has lost its *sikhara* while the Jamli temple still retains its *sikhara* almost intact. The temple faces the east and consists of a shrine surmounted with a *sikhara* and having a portico in front. The *sikhara* is in the Indo-Aryan style of the type of that of the Udayesvar temple at Udaypur (District Bhilsa) or of the Nemawar temple (in Indore State).

44. The question of the conservation of this temple has been engaging the attention of the Department for some years but for one reason or another, the work could not be taken up till the year of report, when the following items of repairs were executed :—

- (1) Jungle was cleared for 50 feet in front and 25 feet on the other three sides including a tree which grew on the temple itself and seems to have been the principal cause of the serious damage to the portico.
- (2) The portico or porch had been badly shattered. The two side pilasters had got displaced. They were properly re-set.
- (3) The lintel of the portico which had cracked was supported on pieces of angle iron $3'' \times 3'' \times \frac{3}{8}''$ placed at the lower corners with ends inserted in notches drilled in the side brackets.
- (4) The broken lintel of the shrine door was supported on a piece of rail iron $5'' \times 4''$ in section.
- (5) The floor of the porch and shrine were re-paved.
- (6) The vertical cracks in the *sikhara* were filled up with cement concrete.
- (7) The premises were levelled up with earthwork and the big stones found in the debris were picked up and arranged in order, round the temple.

(District Shivpuri.)

45 *Chorpura*.—A mediæval Siva temple (10th-11th century A. D.) the ruins of which are visible from the Agra-Bombay Road, near the village Chorpura, was partially conserved in the year of report.

- (1) Jungle in the premises of the temple was cleared,
- (2) The top of the low platform on which the temple stands was levelled up with earthwork. The damaged retaining walls were repaired with dry masonry of big stone blocks.
- (3) The ground around was cleared up and dressed, and carved stones picked up from the site were arranged in the shape of a compound.
- (4) The floor of the shrine room was re-paved with old stone.

- (5) The damaged portions of the basement walls of the temple were repaired.
- (6) A few shaken stones in the *sikhara* were pushed back into their places.
- (7) A footpath was made to connect the temple with the Agra-Bombay Road. The portion of a *nala* where it is crossed by the footpath was filled up with rubble.

46. *Terahi*.—The gateway of the compound of the Mohajmata temple was in a dilapidated condition. The dry stone masonry of the door jambs was dismantled and properly re-built. The lintel was properly re-set. A piece of iron pipe was fixed across the gateway to prevent cattle from trespassing into the compound.

New Construction.

(Caretakers' Huts.)

47. The caretakers' huts at Kakanmadh temple, Suhania (District Morena), at Sondni (District Mandasor), and at Udaygiri (District Bhilsa) which were under construction last year, were completed in the year of report. These huts comprise a room 12' × 10' with a verandah 12' × 7'. The room has two doors, one in the front and the other in the back wall and two windows one in each side wall. The verandah has three openings in front. One of the sides of the verandah is open and the other is closed up with a partition wall. There are two almirahs in the wall of the room. These structures are *pucca*, being built of stone in lime mortar, and the door openings, window openings, pillars and beams being made up of cut stone. The roofs are flat, constructed with stone slabs covered with brick and lime *cheka* and finished with a 5" coat of brick and lime concrete. They make comfortable quarters for the caretakers concerned.

Rest Houses.

48. The Archæological Rest House at the Udaygiri Caves (District Bhilsa) received some attention in the year of report. The slope of the roof of the main room and the two side rooms being insufficient, the rain water was not properly drained, which resulted in the leakage of moisture to the ceiling underneath. The roof was therefore properly sloped by adding an average 3" coat of brick and lime concrete finished with polish.

49. Necessary furniture was purchased for the Rest House at Gyaraspur (District Bhilsa). The Rest House will be duly furnished before next winter.

(ii) Annual Upkeep.

50. Measures of annual upkeep which are due after the rainy season such as jungle clearance, filling up of ruts and pits in the premises caused by the rains, and repairs to footpaths leading to monuments, were carried out at all conserved monuments. The more

important groups of such monuments continued to be maintained in permanent good order through whole time caretakers employed for the purpose.

51. The Rest Houses at Bagh and Udaygiri caves were white-washed and portions of the Gujari Mahal building were treated with white and *doga* wash. Iron and wood work was repainted at the Gujari Mahal (Gwalior Fort), the monuments at Ranod, Surwaya, Terahi (District Shivpuri); and at the Rest Houses at Bagh and Udaygiri caves.

52. The temporary bridge on the river in front of the Bagh Caves was renewed.

53. The *ja'i* panels of the windows and the inscription almirah at the Khokhai monastery at Ranod (District Shivpuri) which had been damaged were repaired. The wooden door frame of the store room at the Jamah Masjid at Chanderi had been eaten up by white ants. It was replaced by a new frame made of cut stone, as a precaution against the repetition of similar damage.

54. The gardens and the plantation of trees at the *Chhattri* of the Rani of Jhansi, the Gujari Mahal and the tomb of Muhammad Ghaus at Gwalior, and at the Bagh Caves (District Sardarpur) were maintained. New rows of *Mehandi* and a few trees were planted at the Gujari Mahal, tomb of Muhammad Ghaus at Gwalior and near the Bagh Caves. Red *bajri* was spread on the footpaths of the *Chhattri* of the Rani of Jhansi garden.

55. At the time of the annual inspection of the Maladevi temple at Gyaraspur (District Bhilsa) on the 5th December 1940 it was found that some miscreants had removed pavement slabs and dug up pits, one in the hall and another in the shrine room of the temple, obviously in search of treasure. The matter was duly reported to the Police but the culprits could not be traced. The pits were repaired in due course.

56. The caretakers of the Surwaya monuments and of the Terahi and Mahua monuments, died in the year of report, and suitable persons were appointed as their successors.

(iii) Approach Roads.

57. No new approach road was made in the year of report. The P. W. D. was moved to metal the fair weather road to the Yasodharman's pillars of victory at Sondni.

(iv) Sign and Notice Boards.

58. The following new sign-boards were made and set up:—

- (1) A big road side sign-board near Badegaon Chowki in the tenth mile of the Morena-Ambah Road calling attention to the Kakanmadh temple (Morena District).

- (2) A small road side sign-board in the fourth mile of the Jawad-Kesarpura Road giving the name and age of the Nau Torana temple.

59. Both the boards are bilingual (Hindi and English), engraved on both sides of stone slabs. Sign-board No. 1 is supported on two stone posts, while sign-board No. 2 on a single one.

60. The stone sign-boards at the following places were re-white-washed and re-inked in black enamel :—

- (a) Gujari Mahal and Chhattri of Rani Jhansi, at Gwalior, (b) Antri, (c) Bhilsa, (d) Chanderi, (e) Gyarpur, (f) Kakpur, (g) Pawaya, (h) Surwaya, (i) Terahi and Udaygiri caves.

61. Printed notices exhibited in frames were renewed at the following monuments :—

- (a) *Garhi* at Surwaya, (b) Khokhai monastery at Ranod, (c) Tombs of Muhammad Ghaus and Tansen at Gwalior.

(v) **Monuments declared protected.**

62. No monuments were declared protected in the year under report.

VI Exploration.

(i) Excavations.

63. In addition to the balance of the grants sanctioned in the two previous years, another instalment of Rs. 5,000 was sanctioned in the year of report for the further development of archaeological excavations. With these funds it was proposed to continue the excavations at the Tila site at Pawaya and at the Garh site at Ujjain and also to tap some other promising sites in the State. But owing to various causes time was not found to carry out the proposed plan in its entirety. No new sites were touched. But the works at Ujjain and at Pawaya which had been left unfinished in previous years (see *Annual Report* for V. S. 1995, paragraphs 43 to 61, and *Annual Report* for V. S. 1996, paras 44 to 49) were pushed on.

Pawaya.

64. Pawaya was taken up first. The excavations at this place were resumed on the 14th January and closed on the 17th April 1941. This was the 4th and so far the biggest instalment of excavations on this site, the three previous instalments having been done in the years 1925, 1934 and 1940.

65. In resuming the work at Pawaya this year, it was only intended to expose the remaining portion of the south face and the whole of the west face of the outermost platform, to clear up the rubbish and the loose debris lying on its top, and then to conserve the monument in the existing condition. But in clearing up the top, an unexpected discovery was made which changed the whole outlook of

the work. When a depression in the south-east portion of the mound was being cleared up, traces of still another platform of ornate design were exposed. When they were followed up, the four sides of a new platform came to light. Thus there are now three platforms. For the sake of easy reference the largest and the outermost platform is named platform No. 1, the new platform discovered this year is given No. 2 and the topmost platform remnants of which had been already exposed in previous operations was numbered 3. Platform No. 3 which measures 53'4" by 53'4" is set on platform No. 2 which is 93'2" by 93'8". Platform No. 2 is completely encased by platform No. 1 which measures 140'6" by 143'. The surviving height of this whole monument is 31'8½" top to bottom.

66. The newly discovered platform No. 2 and platform No. 3 closely resemble each other in the general design, the size of bricks and the style of masonry. Obviously therefore they constitute one contemporary structure. The general design, the size of bricks and the masonry of platform No. 1 differ from those of the other two platforms. The former therefore is apparently a later addition.

67. The face work of platform No. 1 is plain, relieved only by simple offsets carried horizontally. The bricks are thicker (3" to 3½") and better baked than those of the other two platforms. The design of the faces of platforms Nos. 2 and 3 is more ornate. Their bricks are thinner (2" to 3") and not so well baked.

The base of platform No. 2 is plain, broken only with horizontal offsets up to a height of 7½ feet, above ground level. Then there is a large half *gola*, over it is a course of almost square panels flanked by pilasters and inset with a projecting ornamental design. This course of panels is surmounted with another course of bigger panels also flanked by pilasters more ornamental in design and having *ghata* shaped pedestals. At the top of this course of panels is another line of half *gola* supported on a row of small brackets, and carrying in its turn a line of arches resembling in shape the well-known *Chaitya* window common in cave architecture. The portion of the platform above the course of arches has disappeared altogether or damaged. The surviving portion of the face of platform No. 3 consists of a half *gola* carried on plain masonry and supporting a course of panels flanked by ornamental pilasters. The top portion of the platform is missing. The monument is made up of brick work only with the exception of spouts which are of stone. The cementing mortar used is clay mixed with fine sand. The masonry was finished with a thin coat of lime plaster, traces of which have survived here and there. The foundations of platforms Nos. 1 and 2 are made up by ramming a layer of small stone concrete in mud followed by rough brick masonry in founds. In the case of platform No. 1 the thickness of the layer of concrete is about one foot while in platform No. 2 it is six inches. On the other hand, the height of foundation masonry under platform No. 1 is 2' only

while under platform No. 2 it is 4'3". Drains and weep holes have been provided in platform No. 1 for the outlet of air and moisture.

68. The top platform No. 3 represents the shrine proper of the temple, while platforms Nos. 2 and 3 make the plinth or lower terrace on which the shrine was set, leaving a spacious *pradakshina patha* all round. What the design of the superstructure or top of the temple now lost was like, it is difficult to say. No components of *Sikhara* have been found. The top was probably flat and the roof was possibly made up of timber, brick and lime.

A line of square structural pits have been exposed on all sides of platform No. 2. Their purpose is not clear. They are possibly the socket holes for holding timber posts or bases of decorative sculptures.

69. The ideas about this monument are not final as the excavations here are yet incomplete. But judging from the evidence so far unearthed, the history appears to be that there was an earlier monument composed of platforms Nos. 2 and 3, and platform No. 1 was added to it at a somewhat later date. The purpose of the addition is doubtful. It may have been an extension but the complete encasement of an ornamental structure with another with a plain design does not stand to reason. Nor can the encasing be explained as having been necessitated by exigencies of engineering. No portions of platform No. 2 were bulging or had become dilapidated, and required to be strengthened by an encasing structure. Another hypothesis which looks more reasonable is that the later addition was intended to conceal an earlier monument on the ground of religious or dynastic antagonism. According to the former supposition the earlier monument was possibly a Buddhist Stupa and the later addition was intended to transform it into a Brahmanical temple. But no Buddhist relics have been discovered so far in the diggings. The more probable alternative therefore is that a temple built by an earlier dynasty (the Nagas) was covered up by their conquerors (the Guptas) with a temple of their own. The levels of the foundations of the two structures do not differ appreciably. Therefore there was no great interval of time between their ages. A few letters found incised on a piece of brick which from its size and make appears to have come from platform No. 1, are on palæographical grounds assignable to the 5th century A. D. This corroborates the surmise that the transformation of the monument dates from the Gupta period.

That the site of Padmavati was in use for some centuries before that time is indicated by some coins of *circa* 2nd century B. C. picked up from fields around.

70. A stone sculpture of Vishnu in the Gupta style found this year in the excavations would show that the temple was dedicated to that god, while the statue of a Naga king unearthed here last year

perhaps indicates that the earlier temple was a work of the Nagas of Padmavati.

71. No specimens of pottery worth the name and not many coins have been recovered in the excavations. The one important class of antiquities found consists of beautifully modelled *terra cotta* figures, which evidently were used for the surface decorations on the walls of the temple.

72. The Pawaya temple which is composed of two terraces set one upon the other reminds one of the terraced brick temples at Ramnagar (ancient Aichhattra) in the Bareilly District of the United Provinces which is being excavated by the Director-General of Archæology in India.

73. The *terra cotta* finds are mostly busts and heads of human figures with beautiful expressions and fine arrangements of hair. There are some fragments showing the different poses of hands and feet and torsos showing the modes of dress and ornaments. Figures of animals and birds are also among the finds. That the plastic art of clay modelling had developed to its fullest extent is more than proved by these finds which can favourably be compared with similar *terra cottas* recently unearthed in the excavations at Rajghat near Benares.

74. This building continued to be used even during the Muhammadan period, not of course as a temple, but possibly for residential purposes, as indicated by traces of rooms and hearths (*chulas*) of very late period found in the upper portion of the ruins.

75. A fuller description of this part of the excavations has to be reserved for the next year when they are expected to be completed.

76. *Ujjain*.—As originally planned, half and half time and funds were going to be devoted to the excavation works at Pawaya and Ujjain. But the Pawaya work proved more extensive and more fruitful and therefore took more time than was expected. As a consequence, less than desired time could be spared for the work at Ujjain. The Pawaya work was closed on the 17th April 1941. Some time having been taken up by the transport of implements and camp equipment, the work at Ujjain was resumed early in May and closed about the end of that month.

77. During the first instalment of excavations carried out at Ujjain in the year 1939, the ravines and low lying plots on the Garh which is identified with the site of the ancient city had been tapped. During the second instalment this year, on the other hand, high grounds were selected for trial excavations. Trenches were taken in two places. (1) a field in front of the Kripanivas Ram temple and (2) another field situated over a furlong to the north of the temple. These fields formed almost the highest levels in the area, flanked what looked like traces of ancient roads, and were profusely strewn with brick bats and potsherds. It was therefore hoped that the excavation here would reveal remnants of houses flanking the roads.

78. The high grounds chosen for trial trenches proved however to be a handicap rather than an advantage. For we had to dig to a greater depth in order to reach virgin soil. In these two places our digging reached a depth of over 40 feet. The upper ground for a depth of about 20 feet proved almost barren, being made up of heaps of disturbed earth mixed with a sprinkling of brick bats and potsherds. In trenches Nos. 12 and 13 no trace of building was found even at a depth of 41 or 42 feet. Only one or two earthen pots lying on sides were exposed. In trench No. 14 a corner of two brick walls was unearthed at a depth of 22 feet. This will be traced further next season. The structure may be assigned to the Gupta period as one or two *terra cotta* figures in Gupta style were found here at that level.

79. During the excavations of 1939, traces of brick masonry which looked like a drain, had been exposed at the bottom of trench No. 5. The trench was therefore widened this year in the hope of finding more traces of buildings. Fragments of two more brick walls came to light. But no wallings that could be interpreted to constitute a connected building have been discovered in the Ujjain excavations so far.

80. The movable antiquities found at Ujjain this year are of the same type of pottery, stone and shell objects as were unearthed in the year 1939. None of them are of any outstanding artistic or historical interest, to deserve special mention. Ujjain pottery requires further study.

81. The trial excavations made at Ujjain so far have not been very encouraging. We are yet far from success in our search of traces of the ancient city streets and houses, etc. It is found that the site has been very badly disturbed both by nature and by man leaving very little of ancient relics intact. Secondly, we have to dig to an enormous depth to reach relics of ancient times if any have still survived destruction. Consequently excavations here will be prohibitively expensive even if they are fruitful. It is, however, premature to express a definite opinion as to the prospects of large scale excavations at Ujjain until more experiments are made. It is intended to make these trials finally next year. For a list of antiquities discovered in these excavations see Appendix D and for list of photographs refer to Nos. 48 to 229 in Appendix I.

(ii) Listing of Monuments.

82. Some listing work was done in the year of report with a view to find out promising ancient sites for archaeological excavations and for exploring monuments.

83. The Director visited 7 places, namely, Amrol and Barai (in District Gird), Baredi, Kutwar, Paytha and Samantukhera (in District Morena), and Dadur (in District Sardarpur) and the General Assistant and the Photographer visited the 8th place Badher (in District Bhilsa). 8 villages were thus visited and 20 monuments listed, statement of which appears in Appendix E.

84. Kutwar and Samantukhera were visited in search of excavation sites. Both are at least as old as the 4th or 5th century A. D. The ancient site of *Kutwar* identified with Kantipuri, one of the three capitals of the Nagas, is a high mound, part of which is occupied by the existing village and another part has been submerged in the Irrigation Dam on the Asan. The remaining portion which is unoccupied seems to have been disturbed. The prospects of excavations here are therefore not very bright. Still some digging is worth being tried as an experiment.

85. *Samantukhera* is situated about 4 miles to the north-west of Bagchini and about a mile north of Gudha, on the right bank of the Chambal and has been badly dissected by its ravines. That the site dates from the Gupta period can be judged from the large size bricks in the ruins of what appears to be a city fortification wall. The site is a small one, and is now extremely difficult of access owing to the deep ravines by which it is surrounded. There are ruins of a stone temple a small distance to the south of the brick fortifications referred to above. Judging from the pieces of bricks washed down in the ravines and traces of brick and stone masonry peeping out here and there in the banks of the ravines it appears that there were a number of ancient sites in the neighbourhood, but all of them have now been washed away into the Chambal. Among these are the ruins of a mediæval shrine, a broken sculpture of Hanuman and fragments of other stone images, perched on a high peak in the ravines.

✓86. *Amrol* is situated about 8 miles to the south-west of Antri by a cart track. It is also reached by a longer but better route *via* the Harsi canal bank road which branches off from the Gwalior-Jhansi Road near Tekanpur. Amrol is an old village possessing ruins of temples, sculptures and carvings dating back to the 8th or 9th century A. D. These ruins are in three groups. The largest and principal group is about 6 furlongs to the north-west of the village. It consists of two mounds which are the sites of brick temple which have now disappeared. To the north of one of the two mounds stands the Ramesvar temple. The other mound is known as Ganesa Pahadia from an idol of Ganesa lying on it. The site is strewn with fragments of stone sculptures and carvings and Siva *lingas*. If excavated it will probably bring to light a number of mediæval images of Hindu gods and goddesses.

87. Another Hindu temple locally known as Danebaba is situated about a quarter of a mile to the south-east of the village.

88. The third group is a shrine sheltering a large mediæval idol of a goddess locally called Behmata, built on the site of a large Jain temple which has disappeared, leaving behind a number of damaged stone statues of Jain *Tirthamkaras* scattered round about.

89. *Barai*.—There are two groups of ruined Jain temples, one to the north and the other to the south of the village. The former group consists of two temples. One is a single shrine sheltering a very

large sculpture of a Jina. The other temple is made up of three ruined shrines situated at a little higher level. The other group which is situated on the hill to the south of village consists of four shrines standing in a row touching one another. All the shrines shelter big stone idols of Jain *Tirthamkaras*. As seen from the style of architecture and from a dated inscription on the pedestal of an image, these temples are contemporary with the rock cut Jain statues on the Gwalior Fort (15th century A. D.).

90. *Baredi*.—A short distance to the north-east of the village stand the ruins of a Hindu temple, and a well of about the 13th century A. D.

91. *Paytha*.—Near the village is the site of a Jain temple which has disappeared. The site is strewn with a number of mutilated statues of Jain *Tirthamkaras*.

92. *Dadur*.—The village is 3 miles to the S.-E. of the Mangod Dak Bungalow. To the east of the village are the sites of two Jain temples, on one of which is lying a huge stone image of a *Tirthamkara* and on the other an equally huge stone statue of Kubera (Jain). These sculptures are worthy of preservation either on the original sites or at a suitable place in the compound of the Mangod Dak Bungalow.

93. *Badher*.—The assistants who visited this village report that there are sites of two mediæval Hindu temples where a number of mediæval sculptures of Hindu gods and goddesses are standing, some of them half buried in ground. A sculpture of Vishnu and another of Brahma and a huge ceiling slab which bears a lotus flower carved on it are particularly mentioned. The ceiling slab is locally named as Singar Sila after the Singar *gotra* of the local Rajput Zamindar and his kinsmen. The place will be further examined by the Director, as soon as time permits.

(iii) Epigraphy.

94. Eight inscriptions were copied or noticed in the year of report. One of them is in Gupta characters of the 5th century A. D., another in the Nagari characters of the 15th century A. D., while the rest are in old Nagari characters of the mediæval period. All of them are in Sanskrit language.

95. The earliest of these inscriptions which is assignable to the 5th century on palæographical grounds is incised on a piece of brick unearthed in the excavations at Pawaya (District Gird). It merely records the name of an individual—Somadatta, son of Ganga-datta, who was probably a donor or an artisan, connected with the excavated temple.

96. Next in date is a fragmentary stone inscription of about the 12th century A. D., discovered at Chanderi, which is apparently part of a large Sanskrit *Prasasti* probably recording the construction of a

Hindu temple in the regime of or under the patronage of a Pratihara king of Chanderi. The right part of the inscription having been lost, the genealogy of the Pratihara dynasty which is recorded in the recovered portion is incomplete. It has preserved the names of kings Hariraja, Bhima, Ranapala, Vatsaraja and Abhayapala. The complete genealogy of this line of Pratiharas is already known from other inscriptions found at Chanderi and Kadwaha in previous years, from which it appears that the names of (1) Nilakantha (6) Svarnapala, (7) Kirtipala, (9) Govindaraja, (10) Rajaraja, (11) Viraraja and (12) Jaitravarman have perhaps been lost with the missing portion of this inscription.

97. Another inscription discovered this year is engraved on a slab in the pavement of the porch of the Bhutesvar temple in the Garhi at Kadwaha (District Guna). It was noticed after the place was freed from the debris of later accretions. It records that an ascetic named Bhutesvara (from whom the present name of the temple seems to have been derived) renovated the mutilated *Jaladhari* of the Linga (enshrined in the temple) in V. S. 1366 (=A. D. 1309) in the reign of Ala-ud-din Khilji of Delhi. It further records that the same ascetic practised austere penance (with a view to remedy the calamity) when the whole earth had been over-run by the Melechhas.

98. Still another inscription is recorded on the pedestal of a large stone image of a Jain *Tirthamkara* enshrined in a temple on a hill to the south of the village Barai District Gird). It is too badly worn out to be completely deciphered. It is dated in V. S. 1529 (=A. D. 1472) and refers to the Maharaja Kirti Singh Tomara of Gwalior.

99. The remaining four inscriptions are incised on the pedestals of sculptures of Hindu gods and goddesses collected in the Mahakal temple at Ujjain and simply record their names.

100. A statement of these epigraphs is given in Appendix F.

(iv) Numismatics.

101. Two gold, 270 silver and 590 copper, *i. e.*, altogether 862 coins were examined during the year of report.

102. Two of the copper coins were unearthed in the excavations carried out at Ujjain. One is a punch-marked and the other a cast coin assignable to *circa* 2nd century B. C. and 2nd century A. D., respectively.

103. Two hundred and sixty-nine coins comprising 1 gold and the rest silver were received as treasure-trove in five lots of 12, 11, 127, 107 and 12 coins from (1) village Haripur, (2) Dungarpur, (3) Udaypuri, (4) Gaori and (5) Gandhaval, respectively.

104. The gold coin belonged to Jagat Singh II of Jaipur. Of the silver coins 225 were of Jaya Singh Khichi of Bajrangarh, 8 of the rulers of Datia, 8 of the Scindias of Gwalior, and the remaining of

Mughal Emperors, viz., 1 of Akbar, 1 of Jahangir, 5 of Shah Jahan, 14 of Aurangzeb, 1 of Shah Alam I, 3 of Alamgir II, 1 of Shah Alam II and 1 fragment of a coin.

105. Two silver coins of Shah Alam II of Asafabad mint were purchased from the Provincial Museum, Lucknow.

106. Five hundred eighty-three copper coins were purchased from Pawaya. These comprise 4 punch-marked, 4 inscribed cast, and 5 uninscribed cast coins. The cast coins appear to be tribal coins of Padmavati, assignable to the 2nd century B. C. The legends of the inscribed coins are in Brahmi characters, partially obliterated.

107. Naga coins in this lot number 483 representing Bhava Bhima, Brihaspati, Deva, Ganendra, Prabhakara and Skanda Nagas. Ganendra as usual claims by far the largest number of these coins but fortunately the lot has enabled us to make good two types of the coins of Bhava Naga which we had lost in theft.

108. There are 59 Muhammadan coins in this lot. 3 of these belong to the Sultans of Delhi. Ala-ud-din Muhammad Shah II, Mubarak Shah and Ghiyas-ud-din Tughlaq are represented each by one coin. There are 17 coins of the Malwa Sultans—6 coins of Hoshang Shah, 2 of Ghiyas Shah, 2 of Mahmud Shah I, 2 of Nasir Shah and 5 of Mahmud Shah II. There are 2 coins of the Sultans of Gujrat, one of Bahadur Shah and the other of Muzaffar Shah III. There are 3 coins of the Mughal Emperors of Delhi, 2 of Humayun and 1 of Shah Jahan II. And 34 Muhammadan coins remain unidentified owing to incomplete legend.

109. Ten State coins, 1 of Gwalior, 2 of Rutlam and 7 of other States and 16 other mutilated coins make up the complete lot.

110. One copper coin of Humayun and 2 of Ala-ud-din Masud Shah were purchased from the Provincial Museum, Lucknow.

111. One gold and 2 copper coins were received from Pandit Ram Govind of Kotwal. The gold piece is a Kushan coin which cannot be further identified as the legend on it has been obliterated. The two copper coins also are mutilated and hence undecipherable.

112. Out of the 862 coins examined during the year of report 1 gold, 12 silver and 35 copper coins have been acquired for our coin cabinet. For detailed analysis of coins examined and acquired see Appendix G.

VII. Archæological Museums.

(i) The Museum at the Gujari Mahal, Gwalior Fort.

113. Two stone sculptures, 7 *terra cotta* figurines, 2 inscribed clay seals, 1 inscribed brass seal, 1 talisman of gold alloy, 1 palm leaf manuscript, 24 copies of wall paintings from Bagh Caves, 1 miniature painting and 48 coins or 87 antiquities in all were added to this Museum in the year of report.

114. The stone sculptures were picked up from debris cleared from the premises of the caves at Udaygiri (District Bhilsa). The *terra cotta* figures, the seals, the miniature painting and the talisman were purchased. The manuscript was received as a present from Mr. G. D. Sapre of Poona and the coins were either excavated, or received as treasure-trove, as presents, or in exchange.

115. One of the two sculptures which belonged to the mediæval period, is the torso of a bearded figure (Agni?) and the other is a head. The painting represents a Bundela warrior king of the 18th century on horseback. The *terra cottas* which represent human heads and figurines, and the two inscribed seals are reported to come from Rajghat (Benares) and are specimens of the early Gupta art of the 5th century A. D.

116. One brass seal purchased (at Pawaya) bears the name "Rai, son of Sant Chandrabhan," in Nastaliq characters and the figure "22". Who this person Rai was and what the figure 22 is intended to convey it has not been possible so far to find out. The palm leaf manuscript is a portion of the (Sanskrit) text of Skanda Purana in Telugu characters.

117. Among the numismatic acquisitions, 1 punch-marked and 1 cast coin come from Ujjain, while 4 punch-marked, 9 cast and 11 Naga coins come from Pawaya (Padmavati). The remaining 22 coins belong to the Sultans of Delhi, Gujrat and Malwa and to the Mughal Emperors of Delhi.

118. This lot of Naga coins has supplied two types of the coins of Bhava Naga which had been lost in the theft that took place in the Museum in the year 1939. Pandit Ram Govind of Kotwal presented a gold (alloyed) Kushan coin. But it is defaced beyond the possibility of further identification. The remaining coins represent some of the Sultans of Delhi, Gujrat and Malwa and the Mughal Emperors.

119. The Director-General of Archæology in India has kindly lent to our Museum on permanent loan a small set of duplicates of pre-historic antiquities from Mohenjo Daro excavations, for which he deserves our grateful thanks. Our thanks are due also to the other donors Mr. Sapre and Pandit Ram Govind.

120. The copies of Bagh mural paintings were re-arranged in the year of report. Formerly they were exhibited partly in room No. 4 and partly in room No. 13. Now they have all been brought together and exhibited in room No. 4 which was specially constructed for this purpose. Two metal images of Buddhist gods purchased in previous years were exhibited in suitable show cases made of teak wood and plate glass. Other acquisitions which chiefly consist of excavated antiquities from Pawaya, Ujjain and Mohenjo Daro could not be exhibited for want of show cases. These show cases could be purchased only about the close of the year. The waiting antiquities will be exhibited in them as soon as possible.

121. Many of the sculptural exhibits acquired in recent years were without labels. This want was supplied in the year of report with enamel labels similar in make to those which existed already.

122. Important repairs to the terrace floors and parapet walls of the courtyards and to footpaths in the Museum building, were carried out in the year of the report. They are briefly described under Conservation in *para.* 21 above.

123. As the Museum building is rather extensive, many visitors feel tired and find it uncomfortable to see it at one stretch. Two steel and teak wood benches were therefore purchased and placed in suitable places for visitors who wish to rest at intervals. The pot garden of the Museum was further extended and a few masonry flower beds were constructed.

124. The Museum has gained ample popularity and attracts a large number of visitors. Owing to the World War however, a considerable fall has occurred in the number of foreign visitors.

(ii) The Museum at the Mahakal Temple at Ujjain.

125. The premises in which the collection of sculptures has been kept in a wing of the Dharmashala of the Mahakal temple at Ujjain is unsuitable for the purpose. No effort for the further development of the Museum is advisable or even possible till the Museum is shifted to a more spacious and suitable place. A proposal for a new museum building at Ujjain has been under consideration for years, but unfortunately no suitable site has yet been available.

126. Thirty stone sculptures of the mediæval period many of which are fragmentary were added to this collection. Some of these were picked up from various places in and around the city. Others were received from the local Municipality. These latter were unearthed from the foundations dug for the construction of the local Vegetable Market.

127. The statement of antiquities added to Museum is set forth in Appendices H, H1 and H2.

VIII. Publications.

128. *Annual Administration Report* of the Department for the year 1938-39 (V. S. 1995) which was in Press last year was printed and published in the year of report. The *Annual Administration Report* for the year 1939-40 (V. S. 1996) has been in Press, and will be out shortly.

129. Sixteen Picture Postcards of the views of Bagh Caves were printed for sale.

130. A short note on Archæology and Antiquities was contributed for the revised edition of the Commercial and General Directory of Gwalior State, being published by the Department of Commerce and Industries.

131. Proofs of articles on the Tumain Inscription of Kumara-gupta and Ghatotkachagupta and the Mandasor Inscription of Govinda-gupta and Prabhakara contributed to the *Epigraphia Indica* were revised and returned to the Government Epigraphist for India.

IX. Important Events.

132. Important events in the year of report were :—

- (a) A stall of Archæological exhibits was arranged in the Annual Fair as a part of the Art Exhibition.
- (b) State buildings under the care of the Archæological Department were decorated and illuminated on two occasions in the year of report—
- (1) The opening of the statue of the late His Highness Maharaja Sir Madhav Rao Scindia at Lashkar, and
 - (2) the most auspicious ceremony of the marriage of His Highness Maharaja Sahib.
- (c) St. Nihal Singh, Writer and Journalist of international reputation, and his wife visited Gwalior as State guests. They visited the Archæological Museum and the Archæological Monuments on the Gwalior Fort, among other places of interest in Gwalior. Information on Archæology and History relating to Gwalior which Mr. Singh wished to have was supplied to him along with a loan of many reference books.

133. Important archæological monuments in the districts were visited by the following distinguished visitors :—

- (a) *Bagh Caves* :—Mr. G. P. Hirway, pleader, Ujjain, (2) Mr. Gulam Ali Daudbhai of Bombay, (3) Mr. Kalabhai Yusuf Ali, President, Municipality, Dohad, (4) Mr. Safdarali Khan, Suba, Sardarpur, (5) Lieut. N. K. Bhonsle, Chief Engineer, P. W. D., Gwalior, (6) Mr. G. D. Mehta, District Forest Officer, Malwa Prant, Ujjain, (7) Rajyaratna S. V. Mukerjee, Sir Suba and Census Commissioner, Baroda, (8) Rajputri Usha Raja Gaekwad of Baroda, (9) Mrs. Arunadevi Mukerjee, M. A., Baroda, (10) Khan Bahadur Md. Sana Ullah, Archæological Chemist in India, (11) Mr. M. K. Kher, Dewan, Dhar State, (12) Mr. M. B. Retrekar, Inspecting Engineer, P. W. D., Gwalior, (13) Mr. P. S. Mehta, Director, Co-operative Societies, Gwalior, (14) Rai Bahadur M. P. Bhola, Conservator of Forests, Gwalior, (15) Miss L. P. Habert, M. A., (16) Mr. and Mrs. Hamid A. Ali, I. C. S. (Retired), Mussoorie, (17) Capt. Sahibzada Md. Asad Ali Khan, A. D. C. to H. H. the Nawab Sahib Bahadur of Jaora, and (18) Nawabzada M. Abdul Rahim Khan, Shahabad (U. P.), etc., etc.

- (b) *Gyaraspur* :—Mr. M. V. Nabar, D. I. G., Police, Ujjain, and Mr. B. N. Gupta, Forest Officer, Bhilsa.
- (c) *Chanderi* :—(1) Party of students from Sir J. J. School of Arts, Bombay, (2) Mr. Dashrath Singh Chauhan, Supdt. of Police, Guna, (3) Hon'ble Mr. Takhatmal, Minister for Rural Welfare and Local Self-Government, Gwalior, and (4) Mr. M. L. Mital, District and Sessions Judge, Guna, etc.

X. Photographs and Drawings.

134. Two hundred and thirty photographs were taken in the year of report and 277 prints were prepared for the following purposes :—

- (a) For the album submitted with the Annual Administration Report for the Samvat year 1996.
- (b) For office record.
- (c) For supplying demands from scholars and purchasing customers, etc.
- (d) For preparation of half-tone blocks.
- (e) For the Central Religious Endowment Committee.
- (f) For the Secretary to the Promotion of Art and Culture, Amritsar.
- (g) Ten enlargements (17"×23") were prepared for Huzoor Secretary's Office (Publicity Section).

135. No lantern slides were made in the year of report.

136. Eight drawings were prepared and kept in the record.

137. For detailed lists of photographs, and drawings see Appendices I and K, respectively.

XI. Office Library.

138. One hundred and twenty-three Books were added to the office library in the year of report. They comprise publications on Archæology, Art, Architecture, History and allied subjects. Out of these, 56 were purchased and the remaining 67 were received as presents or in exchange from the Government of India, Provincial Governments, Governments of Indian States and Institutions, etc., to whom our thanks are due. See Appendix L.

XII. Expenditure and Income.

139. The expenditure incurred under the different heads of the budget and the income realised from various sources are set forth in Appendices M and N, respectively. Thus the annual expenditure amounted to Rs. 41,666-8-6 and the income to Rs. 374-15-10 in the year of report.

XIII. Concluding Remarks.

140. In conclusion, I am glad to express my sincere gratitude to Rajmantrapravina S. P. Rajgopalachari, Hon'ble the Home Minister, for the keen interest he has evinced in the work of this Department, for his strong and effective support in securing necessary budget grants to meet urgent needs of the Department, and for his never failing courtesy.

M. B. GARDE,
 Director of Archæology,
 Gwalior State.

Appendix A.

Tour Diary of the Director of Archæology, Gwalior State, for the year 1940-41,
Samvat 1997.

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	Remarks.
October 1940.		
17th	Gwalior to Antri and back.	
November		
11th	Gwalior to Badagaon and back.	
25th-26th	Gwalior to Bagh Caves.	
27th-29th	Halt at " "	
30th	Bagh Caves to Indore <i>en route</i> to Ujjain.	
December.		
1st	Indore to Ujjain.	
2nd	Halt at Ujjain.	
3rd	Ujjain to Bhilsa.	
4th	Bhilsa to Besnagar (Khamb Baba) and to Udaygiri and back to Bhilsa.	
5th	Bhilsa to Gyaraspur.	
6th	Halt at "	
7th	Gyaraspur to Bhilsa.	
8th	Visit Udaygiri Caves.	
9th	Bhilsa to Chanderi <i>via</i> Kakpur.	
10th	Halt at Chanderi.	
11th-12th	Chanderi to Gwalior <i>via</i> Surwaya and Shivpuri.	
January 1941.		
9th	Gwalior to Baodipura.	
10th	Halt at "	
11th	Baodipura to Gwalior.	
16th	Gwalior to Pawaya <i>via</i> Antri.	
17th	Halt at Pawaya.	
18th	Pawaya to Gwalior.	
22nd	Gwalior to Bijola (Irrigation Bungalow).	

Appendix A.—(contd.)

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	Remarks
23rd-24th	Bijola to Kotwal and back to Gwalior.	
26th	Gwalior to Pawaya and back.	
29th	„ to Padhavli.	
30th	Padhavli to Mitaoli and thence to Gwalior.	
February.		
3rd	Gwalior to Pawaya.	
4th	Visit Dhumeshwar temple.	
5th	Pawaya to Gwalior <i>en route</i> to Amrol.	
7th	Gwalior to Bagchini.	
8th	Bagchini to Samantukhera.	
„	Visit Paytha and back to Bagchini.	
9th	Bagchini to Gwalior.	
12th	Gwalior to Pawaya.	
13th	Pawaya to Gwalior.	
25th	Gwalior to Pawaya.	
26th	Pawaya to Gwalior.	
March.		
24th	Gwalior to Pawaya.	
25th	Pawaya to Gwalior.	
29th	Gwalior to Pawaya.	
30th	Halt at Pawaya.	
31st	Pawaya to Gwalior.	
April.		
2nd-3rd.	Gwalior to Ramnagar (District Bareilly).	
4th	Ramnagar to New Delhi.	
5th	New Delhi to Gwalior.	
7th	Gwalior to Barai and Panihar and back to Gwalior.	
12th	Gwalior to Pawaya.	
13th-14th	Halt at Pawaya.	
15th	Pawaya to Gwalior.	

Appendix A.—(concl'd.)

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	Remarks.
17th-19th	Gwalior to Bagh Caves.	
20th	Halt at Bagh Caves.	
21st	Bagh to Jamli and Jamli to Mangod <i>via</i> Tanda.	
22nd	Mangod to Dadur and Dadur to Ujjain.	
23rd-24th	Halt at Ujjain.	
25th	Ujjain to Bhilsa <i>via</i> Sonkatch.	
26th	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.	
27th	" to Esagarh <i>via</i> Chanderi.	
28th	Esagarh to Shivpuri.	
29th	Shivpuri to Gwalior.	
May		
5th	Gwalior to Esagarh.	
6th	Esagarh to Kadwaha.	
7th	Halt at "	
8th	Kadwaha to Mahua and Terahi, and back to Kadwaha.	
9th	Kadwaha to Esagarh.	
10th	Esagarh to Ujjain.	
11th-13th	Halt at Ujjain.	
14th	Ujjain to Mandasor <i>via</i> Barnagar.	
15th	Mandasor to Khor <i>via</i> Neemuch and Jawad, and thence to Ratangarh.	
16th	Ratangarh to Singoli and back to Mandasor.	
17th	Mandasor to Ujjain <i>via</i> Barnagar.	
18th-26th	Halt at Ujjain.	
27th	Ujjain to Bagh Caves.	
28th	Halt at Bagh Caves.	
June 1941.		
1st	Bagh Caves to Ujjain <i>via</i> Mhow.	
2nd-3rd	Ujjain to Udaygiri Caves <i>via</i> Sonkatch and Bhilsa.	
4th	Udaygiri Caves to Basoda.	
5th	Basoda to Udaypur and back.	
"	" to Shivpuri.	
6th	Shivpuri to Gwalior.	

Appendix B.

List of Monuments conserved during the year 1940-41, Samvat 1997.

Serial No.	Place.	Name of Monument and detail of work.	Amount sanctioned.		Total.	Amount spent.		Total.	Remarks.
			Current year.	Last year.		Current year.	Last year.		
1	Gwalior	Improvement of the Archaeological Museum building.	Rs. a. p. 1,500 0 0	..	Rs. a. p. 1,500 0 0	Rs. a. p. 1,281 11 9	..	Rs. a. p. 1,281 11 9	
2	"	Removing debris mixed with stones, etc., from the inside passage of north side of Gujari Mahal, Estimate No. 23/97.	350 0 0	..	350 0 0	341 3 9	..	341 3 9	
3	Antri	Repairs to the tomb of Abul Fazl, Estimate No. 9/97.	150 0 0	..	150 0 0	149 9 6	..	149 9 6	
4	Chorpura	Repairs to the Mahadeva temple, Estimate No. 22/97.	120 0 0	..	120 0 0	118 3 11	..	118 3 11	
5	Terahi and Kadwaha.	Conservation of monuments.	..	..	..	..	811 1 0	811 1 0	
6	Chanderi	Repairs to horses' tomb, Estimate No. 11/97.	40 0 0	..	40 0 0	28 2 3	..	28 2 3	
7	Udaygiri	Repairs to steps and foot-path of caves, Estimate No. 12/97.	170 0 0	..	170 0 0	169 15 2	..	169 15 2	
8	"	Repairs to the roof of Rest House of Caves, Estimate No. 13/97.	50 0 0	..	50 0 0	50 0 0	..	50 0 0	
9	"	Additional work of verandah of Caretaker's hut, Estimate No. 24/97.	152 0 0	..	152 0 0	151 1 4	..	151 1 4	

10	Sondni	" " " 26/97.	199 0 0	199 0 0	197 1 6	..	199 0 0	197 1 6	..	197 1 6
11	Khor	Repairs to Nau Toran temple, 8/97.	130 0 0	130 0 0	130 0 0	..	130 0 0	130 0 0	..	130 0 0
12	"	" " " 27/97.	11 0 0	11 0 0	10 11 0	..	11 0 0	10 11 0	..	10 11 0
13	"	Fixing sign-board, Estimate No. (B) 20/97.	12 0 0	12 0 0	11 0 10	..	12 0 0	11 0 10	..	11 0 10
14	Bagh	Temporary wooden bridge on the river near the Caves, Estimate No. 5/97.	25 0 0	25 0 0	25 0 0	..	25 0 0	25 0 0	..	25 0 0
15	"	Special repairs to the Caves, Estimate No. 16/97	10,000 0 0	10,000 0 0	9,091 15 9	..	10,000 0 0	9,091 15 9	606 4 3	9,698 4 0
16	Jamli	Repairs to the Mahadeva temple, Estimate No. 6/97.	199 0 0	199 0 0	122 11 5	..	199 0 0	122 11 5	..	122 11 5
17	Suhania	Construction of caretaker's hut at Kakanmadh temple, Estimate No. 24/95.	..	..	..	..	..	..	198 4 1	198 4 1
18	"	Additional work of verandah of caretaker's hut, Estimate No. 26/97.	198 0 0	198 0 0	197 1 6	..	198 0 0	197 1 6	..	197 1 6
19	"	Repairs to an old well discovered near the Kakanmadh temple.	..	..	..	..	..	..	829 3 11	829 3 11
20	"	Repairs of compound wall at Kakanmadh temple, Estimate No. A 20/97.	41 0 0	41 0 0	40 8 0	..	41 0 0	40 8 0	..	40 8 0
21	Badegaon	Fixing sign-board of Kakanmadh temple at the Badegaon Chowki, Estimate No. 7/97.	106 0 0	106 0 0	100 15 3	..	106 0 0	100 15 3	..	100 15 3
Total..			13,453 0 0	13,453 0 0	12,217 0 11	..	13,453 0 0	12,217 0 11	2,444 13 3	14,661 14 2

Appendix D.

Movable Antiquities found in Archæological Excavations at Pawaya, District Gird, and at Ujjain, in the year 19940-41, Samvat 1997.

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
		(A) PAWAYA.		
		Bone objects.		
1	92	Piece of a bangle.		
	236	„ „ bone and bangle.		
		Terra Cotta objects.		
2		(Divine figures.)		
	22	Three-faced figure (Brahma), seated on lotus, matted hair, two armed, left arm and leg broken off	$6\frac{1}{2}'' \times 7'' \times 4\frac{1}{4}''$	
3	332	Lower portion of goddess (Parvati ?) seated on a lion (?) ..	$1' \times 11'' \times 4''$	
		(Human figures.)		
		Head with laughing or smiling faces.		
	19	Head with laughing face ..	$3'' \times 2''$	
	100	„ „ smiling „ ..	$4'' \times 4\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3''$	
	143	„ „ „ „ ..	$3'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$	
	145	„ „ „ „ ..	$4'' \times 2'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$	
	287	„ „ „ „ ..	$4'' \times 2\frac{1}{4}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$	
	302	„ with laughing face and gaping mouth; lower jaw broken off.	$3'' \times 3'' \times 3''$	
	309	„ with laughing face, damaged.	$2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$	
	310	„ „ smiling „ damaged.	$3\frac{1}{4}'' \times 3'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$	
4		Heads with weeping faces.		
	211	Head with weeping face ..	$5'' \times 4\frac{1}{2}'' \times 4''$	
	268	„ „ „ face, dishevelled hair.	$3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3\frac{1}{2}''$	
	291	„ „ „	$4'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$	
	316	„ „ „	$2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{4}''$	
	333	Head with weeping face and wig.	$4'' \times 3'' \times 3\frac{1}{4}''$	

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
5		Heads with wigs of hair.		
	26	Head with wig of hair, nose broken off	6" × 4½" × 3"	
	124	Head with wig of hair ..	5" × 3" × 3"	
	182	" " " " " ..	5" × 4" × 4"	
	197	" " " " " ..	5½" × 5" × 3½"	
	200	" " " " " ..	6½" × 5" × 3"	
	210	" " " " " ..	7½" × 6" × 4"	
	222	" " " " " ..	5" × 4" × 3"	
	297	" " " " " ..	5½" × 5" × 4"	
6		"Heads" with "curls" of hair.		
	8	Head with curls of hair ..	4½" × 3½" × 3"	
	235	" " " " " ..	4" × 3" × 2"	
	308	" " " " " ..	4½" × 3½" × 3½"	
	311	" " " " " ear-ring in left ear only, necklace (Kantha) round neck	3½" × 3" × 3"	
	314	Head with curls of hair, ear-ring in left ear	4½" × 4½" × 3"	
	321	Head with curls of hair ..	4" × 4" × 4"	
7		230 Head with crown	5½" × 4½" × 4"	
8		Heads with matted hair.		
	126	Head with matted hair ..	2½" × 1½" × 2½"	
	152	" " " " " ..	3" × 2½" × 2"	
	334	" " " " and beard. ..	3" × 2" × 2½"	
	349	" " " " " ..	2½" × 2½" × 2"	
		Heads.		
9		Torsos.		
	39	Fighting warrior, sword in right hand, wearing robe of printed cloth, piece of cloth tied round waist, a dagger in scabbard seen on the right side, head and feet lost	11" × 9" × 3½"	
		24, 40, 49, 144, 174, 175, 198, 204, 209, 223, 248, 249, 266, 267, 269, 292, 303, 306, 312, 313, 315, 335, 336, 354, 355, 356, 357.		

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
	85	Torso, left side view ..	6" × 4" × 2½"	
	296	„ seated	7" × 5" × 3"	
	101, 181, 186, 187, 195, 216, 225, 227, 228.	Torsos.		
10		Upper portions.		
	28	Torso standing in relief, showing right side	7½" × 5" × 3½"	
	37	Torso seated, wearing <i>dhoti</i> , left side view	11" × 8" × 3½"	
	45	Waist of a female figure ..	3½" × 3" × 2½"	
	120	Torso showing belly, right hand resting on hip	5" × 3½" × 3"	
	183	Headless bust of a female ..	6" × 5" × 3"	
	203	Torso	6" × 4½" × 3"	
	288	„ of a female	7" × 5½" × 4½"	
	295	„ hand „ „ chest and right hand	7" × 4½" × 2½"	
	307	Upper half of a figure, elaborate hair-dress	9" × 5" × 5"	
	326	Torso, with hands crossing on chest, armlet on left arm and bracelet on the right wrist ..	7" × 5½" × 4½"	
11		Lower portions.		
	23	Lower portion of a figure, feet broken off	4" × 3¼" × 1½"	
	67	Lower fragment of a torso ? ..	4" × 3½"	
	78	Piece of a figure, showing waist and a folded leg	7" × 6½" × 3"	
	81	Piece of a figure, showing thighs..	5½" × 3½" × 3½"	
	90	Lower half of a warrior wearing <i>janghia</i>	8" × 7" × 2"	
	243	Lower portion of a torso ..	6½" × 4" × 2½"	
	290	„ on a stool attached to another stool	7½" × 5½" × 4"	
	322	Lower portion of a warrior ..	6" × 5½" × 3"	
	327	Lower portion of a figure, showing hips	5" × 4½" × 2½"	

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
12	..	330 Lower portion of a figure (warrior ?) Figures with garments.	6" × 4" × 2½"	
13	..	201 Torso (upper portion) wearing garment of printed cloth .. 265 Torso wearing garment of printed cloth 298 Torso with straps of dress crossing on the chest 339 Torso with spotted garment .. 353 " " " " (Female).	5½" × 4" × 2½" 5½" × 4" × 3" 5" × 3½" × 4½" 7" × 4" × 3" 5" × 4½" × 3"	
14	75, 224, 324 ..	Busts. 171 Bust wearing wig Busts.	7½" × 6½" × 3"	
15	5, 25, 51, 63, 68, 88, 89, 114, 128, 151, 193, 196, 212, 213, 214, 215, 264, 280, 304, 350, and 351.	Headless busts.		
16	..	Shoulders. 21 Piece of a figure, showing back shoulder and arm with armlet.. 135 Piece of a figure, showing shoulders	4 × 3½" × 3" 5½" × 4" × 2"	
17	..	Hands. 263 Hand with bracelet, sleeve of garment of printed cloth .. 343 Hand with bracelet	3" × 2" × 2" 4" × 2" × 1½"	
18	..	Arms. 149 Arms of a figure 191 Complete arm and hand with armlet and bracelet.. .. 192, 277, 325	3" × 3½" × 2" 8½" × 4" × 3" Arms.	
19	..	Waist. 45 Waist of a female figure ..	3½" × 3" × 1½"	
19	..	Legs and thighs. 36 Left thigh and knee of a figure sitting cross legged	8" × 5" × 4½"	

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
		109 Complete right foot with thigh and leg	5" × 3½" × 2"	
		113 Complete left foot with thigh and leg	5" × 4" × 2½"	
20	10, 84, 172, 242, and 341	Legs. Bent leg.		
21		43 Bent leg of a warrior wearing <i>janghia</i> ?	5½" × 4½" × 2½"	
		Folded legs.		
		166 Folded leg of a seated figure wearing <i>dhoti</i>	6½" × 5" × 3"	
22		352 Folded leg of a figure wearing <i>dhoti</i>	5" × 4" × 2½"	
		Knee.		
23		291 Knee of a kneeling figure wearing spotted garment	6" × 5" × 3"	
		Feet.		
24	60, 111, 156, 273, 286, 318 and 342.	"		
		Figures of animals.		
		185 Head of a monkey	2½" × 2½" × 2"	
		317 Fragment of a lion	4" × 3¾" × 2"	
		202 Torso of an elephant.. .. .	7" × 6" × 4"	
		4 Horse running to right, with saddle but no rider	9" × 8½" × 3"	
		83 Piece showing two hind legs of a horse	5" × 2½" × 2½"	
		162 Torso of horse running to right.. .. .	6" × 3" × 2"	
		328 Hind portion of a bull	4½" × 4" × 4"	
		329 Fragment of combination of an elephant and a bull.. .. .	8" × 7" × 3"	
		240 Head of a <i>makara</i> (crocodile)	7½" × 7½" × 3½"	
		301 Upper jaw of a <i>makara</i>	6" × 2½" × 2½"	
		115 Fragment of fish	5½" × 4" × 3"	
		165 " " " "	6" × 3½" × 2"	

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.	
25	169	Leg of a toy figure	$8\frac{1}{4}'' \times 5\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$		
	270	Fish, tail broken off	$6\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3''$		
	..	Birds.			
	69	Fragment of a cock ?	$10\frac{1}{2}'' \times 7\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2''$		
	140	Parrot or pigeon ? a fragment ..	$5\frac{1}{4}'' \times 4\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$		
	146	Pigeon	$6'' \times 3'' \times 5''$		
	217	Torso of parrot or pigeon ? ..	$6\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3''$		
	239	Neck of bird	$6'' \times 3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$		
	241	Parrot or pigeon ? head broken off	$3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 6'' \times 4''$		
	246	Fragment of bird	$10'' \times 5'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$		
	323	Neck of bird	$4\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3''$		
	26	340	Torso of pigeon	$7\frac{1}{2}'' \times 4'' \times 3''$	
14, 53, 102, 247..		.. Fragmentary.			
		Bricks.			
358		Piece of an inscribed brick ..	$9\frac{1}{2}'' \times 8'' \times 3\frac{1}{2}''$		
359 and 360		Large plain entire bricks ..	$1\frac{1}{2}' \times 10\frac{1}{4}'' \times 3''$		
361 and 362		" " " " ..	$1\frac{1}{2}' \times 10'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$		
363 and 364		" " " " ..	$1\frac{1}{2}' \times 9'' \times 2''$		
		Decorative bricks.			
27		2	Piece of decorative brick ..	$5\frac{1}{2}'' \times 4'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$	
		47	" " " " foliage design.	$3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3\frac{1}{4}'' \times 2\frac{1}{4}''$	
	65	" " " " linear "	$7\frac{1}{2}'' \times 4\frac{1}{2}'' \times 1\frac{1}{2}''$		
	79	" " " " ..	$7\frac{1}{4}'' \times \frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{3}{4}''$		
	94	" " " " ..	$6\frac{1}{2}'' \times 3\frac{1}{4}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$		
	103	" " " " ..	$8'' \times 6'' \times 5''$		
	131	" " " " ..	$4'' \times 3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$		
	133	" " " " ..	$6'' \times 3\frac{1}{4}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$		
	134	" " " " ..	$6'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 2\frac{1}{4}''$		
	139	" " " " ..	$6\frac{1}{2}'' \times 6\frac{3}{4}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$		
	159	" " " " round at one end and conical at the opposite end	$7\frac{1}{2}'' \times 7'' \times 2''$		

Append x D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
	190	Piece of decorative brick ..	7½" × 6" × 2½"	
	194	" " " " ..	6½" × 4" × 5½"	
	204	" " " " ..	6½" × 6½" × 2½"	
	206	" " " " ..	8" × 5½" × 2½"	
	219	" " " " ..	6½" × 5" × 2½"	
	257	" " " " ..	6" × " × 3"	
	258	" " " " ..	8" × 3½" × 2½"	
	285	" " " " halfround.	6" × 5" × 3"	
	293	" " " " ..	5½" × 3½" × 3"	
	338	" " " " with floral design	7" × 4" × 2½"	
	1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 12, 13, 17, 20, 27, 29, 32, 33, 35, 38, 40, 41, 44, 46, 48, 56, 58, 59, 61, 62, 64, 66, 68 (a), 71, 72, 74, 76, 77, 80, 82, 86, 93, 94, 95, 96, 97, 98, 99, 104, 105, 106, 107, 108, 110, 112, 116, 117, 118, 123, 127, 129, 132, 136, 137, 138, 141, 147, 148, 150, 153, 154, 155, 157, 160, 161, 164, 167, 168, 170, 173, 176, 177, 178, 179, 180, 205, 230, 231, 232, 233, 237, 238, 255, 256, 259, 260, 271, 274, 275, 282, 283, 284, 299, 305, 331, 345, 346, and 348.	Decorative bricks.		
28	..	Pottery.		
	207	Cup	5½" × 5½" × 2½"	
	208	Piece of cup	6" × 6" × 3"	
	220	Cone or pinnacle	7½" × 3½" × 3½"	
	221	Piece of pipe	9" × 4" × 4"	
	320	Small pot.. ..	2" × 2" × 2½"	
	347	Fragment of vessel with spout.	6" × 6½" × 3"	
	158, 276, 278, 300	Pieces of pottery	..	
29	..	Stone objects.		
	251	Image of Vishnu, four armed ..	3'6" × 2' × 9"	
	253 (a) and 253 (b)	Large makara spout in two parts.	6'9" × 1'1" × 1'1"	

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
30		Fragments of Human figures.		
		11 Piece of chest	5¼" × 2¾" × 1¼"	
		15 Head of figurine with matted hair	3" × 2½"	
		52 Fragment of hand	3½" × 1½" × 2½"	
		55 Fragment of sculpture	10" × 7" × 6"	
		73 Piece of image	8" × 8" × 3¾"	
		91 " " " "	10" × 8" × 4¼"	
		121 " " " "	7½" × 6½" × 3"	
		122 Knot of garment	6" × 6" × 4"	
		130 Eye of image	3½" × 2½" × 3"	
		199 Head	5" × 3¼" × 3"	
		252 Fragment of sculpture	1'9" × 1'3" × 6"	
		319 Head	3" × 3" × 2"	
		18 Wrist of image	5" × 4" × 1½"	
		16 Fragment of hand showing four fingers	3½" × 2½" × 2"	
		34 Foot of image broken into three pieces	8" × 5" × 4"	
31		Figures of animals.		
		57 Head of bull or bear ?	6" × 5½" × 3¾"	
		70 Hoof of elephant's foot	7" × 5" × 4½"	
		254 Garuda (double)	11" × 10" × 10"	
32		Miscellaneous.		
		30 Piece of grinding stone	6" × 7" × 2½"	
		31 Stone piece with two fruits carved on it	5" × 3½" × 2½"	
		125 Carved stone with floral design	3¼" × 2¾" × 1¾"	
		188 Lid of vessel with ornamental top	3¾" × 3¾" × 2"	
		234 Stone with foliage ornament	3" × 2¼" × 1½"	

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
		337	Fragment of inscribed stone (undecipherable)	5" × 3½" × 2"
33	 244, 279 and 344.		Unidentified objects.	
			(b) UJJAIN.	
34			Bone objects.	
		331	Piece of bangle.	
		332	Three carved pieces probably of handle of <i>chowry</i> or staff.	
	178, 319 (a) and 319 (b) ..		Pencils used for painting eyes (?)	
35			Earthen objects.	
			Beads.	
	63, 90, 91, 155, 156, 211, 232, 233, 34, 235, 250, 272, 298, 345, 346, 347, and 348.			
36			Bowls.	
		267	Bowl	4" dia. & 3¼"ht.
		335	Small bowl (<i>Katori</i>)..	1¾" dia. ,, 1" ht.
37			Cups.	
		38	Cup	5" dia. ,, 2½"ht.
		96	"	4" dia. ,, 2"ht.
		248	Fragment of cup ..	6" dia. ,, 3½"ht.
		353	Cup	3½" dia. ,, 2¼"ht.
	52, 143, 145, 180, 199, 248, 265, 266, 299, 340, 350, 351, 352, 354, 355, 356 and 357.		Cups.	
38			Cones or pinnacles.	
		31	Cone or pinnacle ..	1" dia. ,, 1¾"ht.
		77	" " " ..	1" dia. ,, 2¼"ht.
		189	Piece of pinnacle ..	7" dia. ,, 11½"ht.
		190	" " " ..	7" dia. ,, 7"ht.
		203	Polished cone or pinnacle	1¼" dia. ,, 2½"ht.
		263	Pinnacle	3" dia. ,, 6¼"ht.

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
	264	Pinnacle	3" dia. and 7"ht.	
	276	"	8" dia. ,, 12"ht.	
	277	"	7" dia. ,, 6½"ht.	
	278	"	2" dia. ,, 9"ht.	
	159, 184, 191, 192, 210, 264, 316	Cones or pinnacles.		
39		Incense burners.		
	37	Incense burner	4" dia. ,, 3½"ht.	
	152	Piece of incense burner ..	3½" dia. ,, 3"ht.	
	153	" " " "	4" dia. ,, 3½"ht.	
	154	Incense burner	4" dia. ,, 3"ht.	
40		Lamps.		
	21	Lamp with pointed mouth ..	2" dia. ,, 1½"ht.	
	22	" " hole in the centre of bottom	2" dia. ,, 1"ht.	
	42	Lamp	2½" dia. ,, 2¼"ht.	
	43	Lamp	2½" dia. ,, 2¼"ht.	
	46	Lamp	2" dia. ,, ¾"ht.	
	231	Lamp with pointed mouth ..	2½" dia. ,, 1"ht.	
	300	Lamp with pointed mouth ..	2" dia. ,, 1¼"ht.	
	304	" " " "	1½" dia. ,, 1"ht.	
	41, 44, 45, 49, 97, 98, 99, 142, 144, 305, and 306	Lamps.		
41		Lids.		
	8	Piece of lid	5½" × 4½" × 3"	
	200	Lid	4" dia. ,, 1½"ht.	
	4, 34, 53, 101, 201, 301, and 304	Lids (fragmentary).		
42		Pendants.		
	245	Circular pendant	1½" dia. ,, ½"ht.	
	320	Small object with hole (pendant ?)	3" × 2½" × 1½"	

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
43	338	Ornamented object with hole for passing string, probably pendant for cattle	$2\frac{1}{2}'' \times 1\frac{5}{8}'' \times 1\frac{1}{2}''$	
	..	Plates.		
	40	Plate	$5\frac{1}{2}''$ dia. and $2\frac{1}{4}''$ ht.	
	48	Fragment of plate with depression at the bottom and decorated with concentric circular lines ..	$4\frac{1}{2}''$ dia. ,, $1\frac{1}{2}''$ ht.	
	67	Plate	$8''$ dia. ,, $2\frac{1}{2}''$ ht.	
	70	Fragment of plate ..	$5\frac{1}{2}''$ dia. ,, $1\frac{3}{4}''$ ht.	
	75	Fragment of plate decorated like No. 48 above	$4''$ dia. ,, $1\frac{1}{2}''$ ht.	
	138	Plate	$5''$ dia. ,, $2''$ ht.	
	141	Plate	$4''$ dia. ,, $1\frac{3}{4}''$ ht.	
	39 69, 136 137, 139 and 140	Plates.		
	154	Bottom of plate	$4''$ dia. ,, $2''$ ht.	
	223	" "	$3\frac{1}{4}''$ dia. ,, $1\frac{3}{4}''$ ht.	
	224	" "	$3\frac{1}{2}''$ dia. ,, $1\frac{3}{4}''$ ht.	
	244	" " or pot ?	$4\frac{1}{2}''$ dia. ,, $1\frac{1}{2}''$ ht.	
44	..	Polished pottery.		
	134	Circular piece (disc of polished pottery)	$\frac{3}{4}''$ dia. ,,	
	290	Piece of polished pottery ..	$5'' \times 1\frac{1}{2}'' \times \frac{1}{2}''$	
	312	" " " " ..	$1\frac{1}{2}'' \times 1''$	
	313	" " " " ..	$1\frac{1}{2}'' \times 1''$	
	325	Piece of glazed, black pottery vessel.	$5\frac{1}{2}'' \times 1\frac{1}{4}'' \times \frac{1}{2}''$	
	326	" " " " ..	$1\frac{1}{2}'' \times \frac{7}{8}'' \times \frac{1}{8}''$	
	327	" " " " ..	$1\frac{1}{2}'' \times 1'' \times \frac{1}{8}''$	
	328	" " " " ..	$1\frac{1}{2}'' \times 1'' \times \frac{1}{8}''$	
	329	Small highly polished piece of pottery	$1'' \times \frac{5}{8}'' \times \frac{1}{8}''$	
	330	Piece of pottery ..	$3\frac{1}{2}'' \times 1\frac{1}{2}'' \times \frac{1}{4}''$	
	341	" " " " ..	$1'' \times \frac{5}{8}'' \times \frac{1}{8}''$	

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
45	146, 187, 204 and 227	Pieces of pottery.		
	..	Pots.		
	7	Small broken pot	2½" × 3" × 2"	
	10	Pot	3½" × 4" × 4"	
	13	Piece of pot	6" × 3" × 4½"	
	157	Piece of pot	4½" dia. and 3¾" ht.	
	181	Small pot	2½" dia. and 2½" ht.	
	202	Small pot (mouth broken)	2½" dia. and 2½" ht.	
	215	Pot (<i>Lota</i>)	5" dia. and 4½" ht.	
	218	Pot	3½" dia. and 3½" ht.	
	259	Piece of pot with pointed mouth.	4½" dia. and 3½" ht.	
	268	Small pot	3½" dia. and 3½" ht.	
	46	23, 95, 160, 179, 216, 217, 219, 220, 221, 222, 242, 279, 280, 303, 336 and 337.	Small pot	2¾" dia. and 2¾" ht.
..		Pots (fragmentary)	..	
..		Scrubbing brushes.		
268		Scrubbing brush	2½" × 1" × 1"	
294		Scrubbing brush	3½" × 2½" × ¾"	
47	..	Spindle.		
	158	Piece of broken spindle	2½" dia. and 2½" ht.	
48	..	Spout.		
	281	Ornamental spout	2½" dia. and 2½" ht.	
	2, 5, 6, 15, 16, 17, 47, 51 and 76.	Spouts (fragmentary)	..	
49	..	Stands.		
	48A.	Piece of stand	6" dia. and 7" ht.	
	246	Bottom of stand	4" dia. and 9" ht.	
	262	Bottom of stand	4" dia. and 2½" ht.	
	50, 74 and 147	Bottoms of stands (fragmentary).	..	
50	..	Terra cotta objects.		
	9	Front portion of elephant	6" × 4" × 4"	

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number,	Description,	Dimensions,	Remarks.
	B. 150	Bull	4" × 3" × 2"	
	162	Bull	4" × 2½" × 4"	
	213	Bull	2½" × 2½" × 1½"	
	193 and 260	Bulls		
	214	Horse	4" × 1½" × 3½"	
	243	Horse	3½" × 2" × 4"	
	249	Wheel of toy cart	1½" dia. and ¾" ht.	
51		Humau figures.		
	163	Head, mouth gaping and tongue issuing out.	1½" × ¾" × 3"	
	183	Head, mouth gaping and tongue issuing.	1" × ½" × 1½"	
	270	Bust with ear-ring and hair-dress.	3½" × 1½" × 1½"	
	319	Upper half of female ..	3" × 1½"	
	344	Head with ornamental wig of hair.	2½" × 2" × 1½"	
	212	Torso of female with folded hands.	5" × 3½" × 2½"	
	257	Torso of male standing.	..	
	161	Legs.	..	
52		Vessels.		
	24	Bottom of vessel	7" × 6" × 2"	
	25	Bottom of vessel	4" × 4" × 2½"	
	26	Bottom of vessel	4½" × 4½" × 2"	
	36	Bottom of vessel	4" × 4" × 1"	
	14, 68, 140, 215 a and 308	Bottoms of vessels .	..	
	27, 28, 29, 71, 72, 73 and 92	Necks of vessels	..	
	100, 194, 195, 196, 197, 198, 225, 226 and 261.	Necks of polished jugs or flower vases ?.	..	
	29d	Piece of decorated vessel ..	8" × 5" × 1"	
	30	Piece of decorated vessel ..	7" × 3" × 1½"	
	65	Vessel with spout	9" dia. and 8" ht.	
	66	Vessel with spout	9" dia. and 8" ht.	

Appendix D.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
53	93	Vessel with spout (mouth broken off).	5½" dia. and 5½" ht.	
	94	Vessel with spout (mouth broken off).	4½" dia. and 4" ht.	
		Weights.		
	271	Circular disc (weight ?)	2½" dia. and ⅝" ht.	
	295	Circular weight	1" dia. and ½" ht.	
	295 a	Circular weight	½" dia. and 1" ht.	
	311	Circular weight ?	1½" dia. and 1½" ht.	
54	339	Circular weight	2" dia. × 1½" ht.	
		Miscellaneous.		
	29 a and c	Fragments of basin	14" × 7" × 4"	
	149	Fire work piece (modern) ? ..	2½" dia. and 4" ht.	
	182	Fire work piece (modern) ? ..	1½" dia. and 2½" ht.	
	241	Musical instrument (<i>damaru</i>) ..	2" dia. and 1¾" ht.	
	247	Jug	5½" dia. and 7" ht.	
	286	Tile	10" × 8" × 1"	
	287	Pieces of mud plaster from wall of bamboo structure.	..	
	289	Piece of brick with socket hole to hold pivot of door.	8" × 7" × 2½"	
	293	Piece of tile with two holes ..	4" × 4" × ½"	
	307	Potter's tool	3" dia. and 3" ht.	
	317	Piece of pipe	½" dia. and 2" ht.	
	318 and 333	Pieces of plaster tile with blue enamel surface (later).	..	
	258, 292 and 309	Unidentified objects.. ..	..	
55		Shell Objects.		
	3, 18, 19, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 78, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 102, 103, 104, 105, 106, 107, 108, 109, 110, 111, 112, 113, 114, 115, 116, 117, 118, 119, 120, 121, 122, 123, 124, 125, 126, 127, 128, 129, 130, 131, 164, 165, 166, 167, 168, 169, 170, 171, 172, 173, 174, 175, 176, 205, 206, 207, 208, 209, 229, 230, 236, 237, 238, 239, 240, 252, 253, 254, 255, 282, 283, 284, 285 and 302.	Pieces of bangles.	..	

Appendix D.—(concl'd.)

Serial No.	Register Number.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
	87 and 117	Pieces of ear-rings		
	55	Shell object		
	35, 35 a, 88, 132, 151, 177, and 228.	Pieces of conch		
56		Stone object.		
	20, 35 and 188	Balls		
57		Beads.		
	256	Seven (Stone or shell ?) beads of a necklace.		
	323	Polished circular bead ..		
58		Human figures.		
	33	Goddess carved on plaque of slate stone, squatting, holding branches of corn in both hands raised up, third eye on forehead, peculiar dress and head-dress.	3" × 2" × 3"	
	32	Snake in relief, carved on plaque of slate stone.	5½" × 2½" × ¼"	
	150 a.	Figure of buffalo (or boar ?) of slate stone	2" × 1½" × ¼"	
	54	One of the two counter parts of a mould of ear-ring (slate stone).	2½" × 2" × ¼"	
	291	Piece of bowl decorated with carving.	2½" × 1½" × ⅛"	
	275	Figure of flying garland bearer..	3½" × 2½" × 1"	
59		Highly polished cylindrical objects probably weights. ?		
	12, 89, 150, 185, 251 and 342	Miscellaneous.		
60		133 Piece of a bangle.		
	186	Natural formation of flint like a crucible.	1" × 1" × 1"	
61		Metal objects.		
	272 a.	A Punch marked coin (?).		
	273	Copper needles (two) ..	(1) 5" long and (2) 3" long.	
62		Oxidised iron objects.		
	296	Ring (<i>Kada</i>)	5" dia.	
	297	Four iron bars	Three 5" long and one 6" long.	
	358	Iron pan (?)	4½" × 3½" × ¼"	
	359	Scythe	7½" × 1½" × ¼"	
	360	Knife	9" × 1½" × 1½"	
	361	Iron padlock	10" × 3" × 2"	

Appendix E.

Monuments listed in the year 1940-41, Samvat 1997.

S. No.	Name of Place.	Name of Monument.	Class.	Remarks.
(District Bhilsa).				
1	Badher ..	Site of a temple with a number of sculptures ..	II	
2	" ..	A big ceiling slab with a lotus flower carved on it and locally known as Singar Sila.	II	
3	" ..	Traces of a temple and cave on the old site of village.	III	
(District Gird-Gwalior).				
4	Amrol ..	Ramesvar temple	I	
5	" ..	Ganesa Pahadia strewn with sculptures and carvings.	III	
6	" ..	Behmata temple and site of a Jain temple ..	III	
7	" ..	Dane Baba temple	III	
8	Barai ..	Ruins of a Jaina temple sheltering a huge image of Tirthamkara on the N. W. of village.	II	
9	" ..	Ruins of another Jaina temple consisting of three shrines in a row near No. 8. above.	II	
10	" ..	A Jaina temple consisting of four shrines in a row, on hill to the south of village.	I	
(District Morena).				
11	Baredi ..	A mediæval shrine in ruins	III	
12	" ..	An old round well near No. 11 above in ruins ..	III	
13	Kutwar ..	A <i>Garhi</i> in ruins	III	
14	" ..	Ancient sites for excavations.. .. .	III	
15	" ..	A mound on the river bank known Surjawa about a mile to the N. E. of village, possible site for excavation.	III	
16	Paytha ..	Site of a Jain temple on the S. E. outskirts of village with a number of sculptures of Jaina Tirthamkaras scattered around.	III	
17	Samantukhera.	Ruins of an ancient brick town now cut up into ravines on the banks of the Chambal about a mile to the N. W. of village Gadha.	III	
(District Sardarpur).				
18-20	Dadur ..	The three different sites of Jain temples strewn with stone images two of which are very large and worth being preserved.	II	

Statement showing the List of Inscriptions Copied or

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.
1	2	3	4	5	6
District Gird.					
1	Panihar ..	On a standing Jaina image in the third shrine from the north in the group of four shrines, on hill.	5	Nagari.	Hindi.
2	Pawaya ..	On a piece of a brick excavated at Tila site.	2	Gupta.	Sanskrit.
District Guna.					
3	Chanderi..	On a broken slab in two pieces (probably a lintel) found in debris in an open space flanking a road in the town.	8	Old Nagari.	"
4	Kadwaha.	On a slab in the pavement of Bhuteshwar temple in the <i>Garhi</i> .	7	Deva-Nagari.	"
District Ujjain.					
5	Ujjain ..	On the pedestal of an image in the Mahakala Museum.	1	Old Nagari.	"
6	"	Do.	1	"	"
7	"	Do.	1	"	"
8	"	Do	3	"	Sanskrit.

No. F.

Noticed during the Year ending 30th June 1940-1941, Samvat 1997.

Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	Remarks.
7	8	9	10
Maharaja Kirat Singh.	Vaisakh Sudi 6 V. S. 1529= A. C. 1472.	Besides giving the year, month and date, and the name of Maharaja Kirat Singh Deva it enumerates the names of several Jaina devotees which are more or less illegible. The date probably is the date of the installation of the idol while the names are those of the donors.	24" × 6½"
..	..	Records the name of Somadatta (son of) Gangadatta (probably a donor or an artisan).	5½" × 6½"
Abhayapala son of Vatsaraja.	No date is found in the recovered portion but <i>circa</i> 12th cent. A. C. on palaeographical grounds.	This record being only fragmentary, its object cannot be made out. Apparently it is a part of a <i>prasasti</i> recording the construction of a Hindu temple, built under the patronage of or during the regime of some king of the Pratihara dynasty of Chanderi whose genealogy commencing from Maharaja Hariraja to Abhayapala is found in the recovered portion of the inscription. The names of Kings mentioned are:—Hariraja, Bhima, Ranapala, Vatsaraja and Abhayapala.	5" = 5" × 6½"
Emperor Ala-ud-din.	Thursday, Magha Sudi 11 V. S. 1366= A. C. 1209.	Records that an ascetic named Bhutesvara replaced with a new one the <i>Jaladhara</i> of (the <i>Linga</i>) in the temple (of this name) on the date specified in the reign of Patashahi Ala-ud-din. It also records that the ascetic practised austere penance when the whole earth had been overrun by the Mlechchhas.	1'9" × 1' not yet copied.
..	..	Records the name of the god or goddess which is mostly illegible.	4" × ¾"
..	..	Illegible.	2¾" × 1"
..	..	A name like <i>beti-padma?</i> is written.	2¼" × 1½"
..	..	Text:—L. 1. श्रीस्कंदिलबालान्वये. L. 2. साभरल्ल-भावां गीरी. L. 3. प्रणमति नित्यं : ॥	3" × 1½"

Appendix No. G.

List of Coins examined during the Year 1940-41, Samvat 1997.

S. N.	King.	Date.	Mint or type.	Metal.	No. of Coins.	Remarks.
I. Found in excavations at Ujjain.						
1	Punch marked ..		Obv. a flower Rev. Avanti symbol	Copper.	1	Acquired
2	Cast, Avanti ..		Obv. horse to r, Rev. Avanti symbol	"	1	"
II. Received as Treasure-trove.						
<i>(a) From village Haripur.</i>						
3	Shah Jahan ..	A. H. 1066	Surat ..	Silver.	1	"
4	Aurangzeb ..	A. H. 1089	Khambayat ..	"	1	"
5	" ..	A. H. 1103	Surat ..	"	1	"
6	" ..	A. H. 1112	" ..	"	1	"
7	" ..	A. H. 1113	" ..	"	1	"
8	" ..	A. H. 1114	Dar-ul-Khair (Ajmer)	"	1	"
9	" ..	"	Akbarnagar ..	"	1	"
10	" ..	A. H. 1116	Surat ..	"	1	"
11	" ..	R. Y. 15	Surat ..	"	2	Returned
12	" ..	A. H. 1099?	Surat ..	"	1	"
13	Shah Alam I ..	A. H. 1120	Junagarh ..	"	1	Acquired
<i>(b) From village Dungarpur, District Morena.</i>						
14	Alamgir II ..	1174		"	1	Returned
15	" ..	1		"	2	"
16	Baijabaï Scindia ..	R. 22		"	1	"
17	Jankojirao ..	..		"	4	"
18	Jayajirao I ..	..		"	3	"

Appendix No G —(contd.)

S. N.	King.	Date.	Mint or type.	Metal.	No. of Coins.	Remarks.
			(c) From village Udaypuri, Thikana Raghogarh			
19	Jagat Singh II of Jaipur.	..	Sawai Madhopur ..	Gold ..	1	Returned
20	Jaya Singh Khichi of Bajrangarh.	..	Jayanagar ..	Silver ..	126	..
			(d) From village Gaori, Thikana Raghogarh.			
21	Jaya Singh Khichi..	..	Jayanagar ..	Silver ..	99	..
22	Seondha in Datia State.	..	Seondha ..	..	8	..
			(e) From village Gandhaval, Jagir Sardar Angre.			
23	Akbar ..	..	..	Silver ..	1	Returned
24	Jahangir ..	..	..	..	1	..
25	Shah Jahan ..	A. H. 1062	..	..	1	..
		5				
26		..	..	..	3	..
27	Aurangzeb ..	A. H. 1075	..	..	1	Acquired
		3				
28		..	..	..	3	Returned
29	Shah Alam II ..	..	..	..	1	..
30	One piece of a coin..	..	..	..	1	..
			III. Purchased at Pawaya			
			(a) Punch marked coins.			
31	Punch marked ..	..	Obv. solar and other symbols Rev. Caduceus indistinct	Copper.	4	Acquired
			(b) Inscribed cast coins probably Tribal: Padma vi.			
32	Cast ..	..	Obv. Leg. tentatively reads as मसत दिव in Brahmi script.	Copper.	1	Acquired
			Rev. symbols indistinct			
33		..	Obv. Leg. tentatively reads as मवपुत in Brahmi script.	..	1	..
			Rev. plain ..			
34		..	Obv. Leg. tentatively reads as मतस in Brahmi script.	..	1	..
			Rev. symbols indistinct			

Appendix No. G --(contd.)

S. n.	King.	Date.	Mint or type.	Metal.	No. of Coins.	Remarks.
35	Cast	..	Obv. a flag and symbols Rev. letters in Brahmi script and Avanti symbol (c) Cast coins-Tribal ..	Copper.	1	Acquired
36	Avanti or Tribal ..	..	Obv. <i>chaitya</i> , tree in railing and other symbols Rev. Avanti symbol ..	Copper.	1	Acquired
37	Cast	..	Obv. A <i>chaitya</i> .. Rev. defaced, a letter in- distinct.	"	1	"
38	"	..	Obv. A standing human figure Rev. A symbol indistinct	"	1	"
39	"	..	Obv. A tree .. Rev. Avanti symbol indis- tinct.	"	1	"
40	"	..	Obv. A monkey-like figure Rev. obliterated .. (d) Naga Coins. ..	"	1	"
41	Bhava	..	Obv. bull to r Rev. Leg. and <i>trisula</i> ..	Copper.	2	Acquired
42	"	..	Obv. bull to r. .. Rev. legend and <i>trisula</i> ..	"	2	Dupli- cates.
43	"	..	Obv. bull to l. .. Rev. Leg and <i>trisula</i> ..	"	2	Acquired
44	"	..	Do ..	"	9	Dupli- cates.
45	"	..	Obv. <i>trisula</i> .. Rev. Leg ..	"	6	"
46	"	..	Obv. " ..	"	2	Acquired
47	Bhima	..	Obv. peacock to l. .. Rev. Leg. indistinct ..	"	2	Dupli- cates.
48	Brihaspati	..	Obv. bull to r. .. Rev. leg ..	"	1	"
49	"	..	Obv. bull to l. .. Rev. leg ..	"	3	"
50	Deva	..	Obv. wheel with spokes .. Rev. Leg. ..	"	12	"
51	Ganendra	..	Obv. bull to r. .. Rev. Leg ..	"	2	Acquired
52	"	..	Obv. tree within a circle of dots .. Rev. Leg. ..	"	1	"

Appendix No. G.—(contd.)

S. N.	King.	Date.	Mint or type.	Metal.	No. of Coins.	Remarks.
53	Ganendra ..	..	Obv. bull to l. Rev. Leg. Maharaja Sri Ganapendra	Copper.	20	Dupli- cates.
54	" ..	..	Obv. bull to l. Rev. Leg. Maharaja Sri Ganendra	"	41	"
55	" ..	..	Obv. bull to l. Rev. Leg. Maharaja Sri Gana	"	62	"
56	" ..	..	Obv. bull to l. Rev. Leg. Maharaja Sri Ga.	"	223	"
57	" ..	..	-	"	88	defaced.
58	Pun ..	..	Obv. lion to l. Rev. Leg.	"	2	Acquired
59	" ..	..	Obv. bull to r. Rev. Leg.	"	1	"
60	Skanda ..	..	Obv. peacock Rev. Leg.	"	2	Dupli- cates.
61	Indo-Sassanian or Gadhैया.	..	(e) <i>Indo-Sassanian</i> Obv. debased face. Rev. altar and dots, etc	Copper.	1	Dupli- cate.
62	Mihirabhoja of Kanauj.	.	(f) <i>Mihirabhoja of Kanauj.</i> Obv. altar, etc. Rev. Leg. Vana. (g) <i>Sultans of Delhi.</i>	Copper.	1	Dupli- cate.
63	Alaud-din Muham- mad Shah II.	..	..	Copper.	1	Dupli- cate.
64	Mubarak Shah ..	..	..	"	1	"
65	Ghiyasud-din Tughlaq.	A. H. (7)22	.. (h) <i>Sultans of Malwa.</i>	"	1	"
66	Hoshang Shah ..	..	..	Copper.	6	Dupli- cates.
67	Ghiyas Shah ..	..	..	"	2	"
68	Mahmud Shah I ..	..	..	"	2	"
69	Nasir Shah ..	..	..	"	2	Acquired
70	Mahmud Shah II ..	A. H. 922	..	"	1	"
71	" ..	..	..	"	4	Dupli- cates.

Appendix No. G.—(concl.)

S.No.	King.	Date.	Mint or type.	Metal.	No. of Coins.	Remarks.
<i>(i) Sultans of Gujrat.</i>						
72	Bahadur Shah ? ..	A. H. 938 or 948.		Copper.	1	Acquired
73	Muzaffar Shah III..	A. H. 977?		"	1	Duplicate.
<i>(j) Mughal.</i>						
74	Humayun ..	A. H. 937.	Agra ..	Copper.	1	Acquired
75	" ..	..	..	"	1	Duplicate.
76	Shah Jahan II ? ..	..	Bhopal ? ..	"	1	Rejected.
77	Muhammadan coins.	..	..	"	34	Unidentified
78	Jayajirao I Scindia.	..	..	"	1	Duplicate.
79	Rutlam State ..	..	..	"	2	Rejected.
80	Other State coins unidentified.	..	..	"	7	"
81	Mutilated: unidentified.	..	..	"	16	"
IV. Purchased from Lucknow Museum.						
82	Alaud-din Masud Shah, Sultan of Delhi.	..	..	Copper.	2	Acquired
83	Humayun ..	A. H. 943	Agra Darul Aman ..	"	1	"
84	Shah Alam II ..	R. Y 18.	Asafabad ..	Silver..	1	;
85	" ..	R. Y. 21	" ..	"	1	"
V. Received as present from Pandit Ram Govind of Kotwal.						
86	Punch marked defaced.	..	..	Copper.	1	Rejected.
87	Kushan (king unidentified).	..	..	Gold ..	1	Acquired
88	A Muhammadan coin legend obliterated and hence unidentified).	..	..	Copper.	1	Rejected.

Appendix H.

Antiquities added to the Archæological Museum during the
Year 1940-41, Samvat 1997.

S. No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Size.	Remarks.
1	2	3	4	5
		Archæological Museum, Gujari Mahal (Gwalior Fort).		
1		Bundela Raja of Rajpur (painting).	14 $\frac{1}{4}$ " $\times$ 18 $\frac{1}{4}$ "	Purchased.
		Sculptures.		
2	Udaygiri ..	A face	4 $\frac{1}{2}$ " $\times$ 2 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	
3	" ..	A torso	1"9" $\times$ 7 $\frac{1}{2}$ " $\times$ 3	
4	" ..	Palm-leaf Manuscript, <i>Skanda Purana</i> in Telugu and Canarese.	..	Presented.
		Seals.		
5	Pawaya ..	An inscribed brass seal ..	..	Excavated.
6	" ..	A gold talisman (alloyed) ..	..	"
		Terra cottas.		
7	" ..	Female figure standing ..	3 $\frac{1}{2}$ " $\times$ 1"	Purchased.
8	" ..	" " " ..	2 $\frac{1}{2}$ " $\times$ 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
9-13	" ..	Faces	..	"
14-15	" ..	Seals inscribed	..	"
		Coins.		
16	" ..	One gold coin	..	Presented.
17-28	" ..	12 silver coins	..	"
29-63	" ..	35 Copper coins	..	"

Appendix H. 1.

List of selected duplicates of Mohenjo Daro Antiquities received on loan from the Director General of Archæology in India and exhibited in the Archæological Museum, Gwalior.

Serial No.	Register No.	Description.	Remarks.
Terra cotta figurines, animals, etc.			
1	D. K.	Male figure.	
2	D. K. 6572	Mother goddess.	
3	H. R. 2537	"	
4	D. K. 7310	"	
5	H. R. 535	"	
6	D. K. 2064	"	
7	D. K. 5134	"	
8	H. R. 1359	"	
9	D. 454	Short horned bull.	
10	C. 3029	Bull garlanded.	
11	S. D. 2502	Bull Brahmani (?)	
12	D. K. 6944	" " (?)	
13	E.	Bull short horned.	
14	O.	Buffalo.	
15	D. K.	"	
16	D. K. 1645	Ram.	
17	H. R.	Bird on pedestal (F).	
18	D. K. 9363	Whistle in the form of a hen on pedestal with hole in the tail.	
Pottery, Plain and Decorated.			
19	D. K. <u>5706</u> D.	Jar or vase.	
20	D. K. 7683	"	
21	O. 2 12.	"	
22	D. K. 12253	"	
23	E. 1666	" small.	
24	D. K. 6104	"	
25	E. 427	"	

Appendix H. 1. —(contd)

Serial No.	Register No.	Description.	Remarks.
26	D. K.	Jar or vase.	
27	L. 547	"	
28	C. 2809	"	
29	D. K. 10332	Flared mouthed vase.	
30	H. R. 5106	Tumbler or vase.	
31	L. 910	"	
32	C. 2070	"	
33	V. S. 2400	"	
34	E. 1003	"	
35	E. 1065	"	
36	V. S. 1706	"	
37	H. R. $\frac{36}{\times}17$	" beaker	
38	D. K. 5105	"	
39	E. 457	"	
40	D. K.	Vase with pointed bottom.	
41	D. K. 164	"	
42	C. 7335	"	
43	C. 2122	"	
44	V. S. 2983	"	
45	V. S. 128	"	
46	V. S. 3174	"	
47	D. K. 1464	Wide shouldered vase.	
48	V. S.	Vase or Handi.	
49	V. S. 7910	" with body trimmed while on tee wheel.	
50	D. K. 9272	" " " smaller.	
51	D. 381	Pedestal vase.	
52	B. 199	Perforated heater	
53	D. 576	Dishes or saucers (F).	

Appendix H. 1.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register No.	Number Description,	Remarks.
54	L. 894	Dishes or saucers (F).	
55	V. S. 82	L'id or Jar cover (F).	
56	H. R. 1186	"	
57	H. R. 5731	"	
58	V. S. 2883	Miniature lids.	
59	H. R. 2136	"	
60	H. R.	Fragment from the moulded stem of an offering stand.	
61	H. R. 6033	Offering stand (F).	
62	D. K. 1930	"	
63	H. R. 5736	Miniature offering stand fitted with the top pan.	
64	H. R. 20	" (F).	
65	O.	Toy framed cart (F).	
66	H. R. 2550	Wheels of toy cart,	
67	C. 650	"	
68	D. K. 51	Balls or marbles.	
69	H. R. 1414	Fragments of bangles, of black colour, may be of stone.	
70	D. K.	" "	
71	V. S. 969	Bangle or bracelet.	
72	H. R. 1660	"	
73	O.	"	
74	E.	"	
75	H. R. 733	"	
76	V. S. 3630	"	
77	O.	"	
78	D. K.	"	
79	D. 172	"	
80	D. K. 6194	"	
81	S. D.	"	

Appendix H. 1.—(contd.)

Serial No	Register No.	Description.	Remarks.
82	S. D. 323	Tubular beads (shape long barrel cylinder).	
83	O.	" " "	
84	O.	Beads.	
85	O.	"	
86	D. K.	"	
87	B. 60	"	
88	O.	"	
89	30	"	
90	H. R. 3222	"	
91	O.	"	
92	H. R. 3711	"	
93	V. S. 1435	"	
94	C. 2083	"	
95	O.	Cones of unknown use with a small knob or projection at base.	
96			
97	B. 697	Cones of unknown use with a small knob or projection at the base.	
98	D. K. 1314	"	
99	D. M.	"	
	O.	"	
100	O.	Cones same as above but burnt to black.	
101	1138	" " "	
102	D. K. 1068	Cone marked with pittings.	
103	S. D. 3600	Cones with middle body scarred with lime.	
104	D. K. or E.	Cones with lines scarred near base (with a hole).	
105	S. D. 1005	" "	
106	L. 144	" " pointed base	
107	V. S. 692	" " (half black).	
108	D. K. 1186.	Pot-sherds painted with horizontal black or red slip.	
109	H. R. 3616	"	

Appendix H. 1.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Register No.	Description.	Remarks.
110	C. 2640	Pot-sherds painted with tree pattern.	
111	S. D. 1232	" "	
112	O.	" "	
113	D. K.	" palm leaf pattern.	
114	C. 2720	"	
115	D. K. 6278	" with intersecting circles pattern.	
116	D. K. 5830	" " "	
117	O.	" " "	
118	D. K. 7369	" " "	
119	E. 2034	" " "	
120	D. K. 2442	" of various other designs.	
121	D. K. 6958	" "	
122	D. K. 7439	" "	
123	D. K. 6860	" "	
124	V. S. 2436	" "	
125	S. D.	Large brick.	
126	D. K.	Standard brick	
127	D. K.	" "	
128	D. K.	Small "	
129	V. S.	Smaller "	
Stone Objects.			
130 to 139	D. K. 5505 V. S. 1760 V. S. 3245 L. 544 D. K. 8551 H. R. 337 V. S. 3108 D. K. 13033 H. R. 2292 B. 466	Weights of various sizes.	
140	H. R. 267	Chert of flint, cone.	
141	V. S. 1968	"	
142	V. S. 1121	"	
143	O.	" flakes.	
144	B.	" "	
145	V. S. 2815	" "	

Appendix H. 1.—(concl'd.)

Serial No.	Register No.	Description.	Remarks.
146	V. S. 212	Chert or flint; flakes.	
147	B. 331	"	
148	D. K.	"	
149	D. K.	"	
150	H. R. 5752	" (broken).	
151	O.	" "	
152	H. R. 3076	" "	
153	D. K.	" "	
154	D. K. 822	" "	
155	B. 533	" "	
156	E.	" "	
157	V. S. 3290	" "	
158	H	" "	
159	H. R. 3856	" "	
160	D. K.		
161	V. S. 3337	" but with one end pointed.	
162	H. R. 5561	"	
163	D. K. 2085	Stone ball or marble.	
164	D. K. 9807	"	
		Faience and paste objects.	
165	C. 2938	Fragments of faience bangles.	
166	D. K. 3139	" but without greenish blue glaze	
167	O.	"	
168	D. K. 2424	Fragment of a vessel, with knotted decoration on the outside.	
169	D. K. 3068	Faience piece without glaze.	
		Shell and shell objects.	
170	D. K. 168	Shell from which bangle has been cut away.	
171	D. K. 2020	Shell bangle.	
172	D. K. 2332	"	
173	D. K. 1325	"	
174	D. K. 1651	One T-C. vase.	
175	D. K. 966	"	
176	D. K. 10001	Shell bangle.	
177	D. 2957	Shell bangle.	
178	D. K. 1517	" unfinished.	
		Beads, pendants etc.	
179	D. K. E.	Thin circular inlay.	
180	D. K. E.	"	
181	D. K.	Thin and small circular paste beads.	
to	D. K.		
195			
		Miscellaneous objects.	
196	L. 855	Wheat charred.	

NOTE.—Register number represents the number in the Register of antiquities received from the Director-General of Archaeology in India, New Delhi,

Appendix H. 2.

List of Antiquities added to the Mahakal Temple Museum, Ujjain, during the Year 1940-41, Samvat 1997.

S. No.	Description.	Size.	Remarks.
1	Lower part of human figure sitting cross legged (inscribed)	15" × 14" × 7"	
2	Siva Parvati	18" × 12" × 6½"	
3	Bust (human)	12" × 12" × 7"	
4	Torso (human)	9" × 8" × 3½"	
5	Siva-Parvati	20" × 17" × 8"	
6	God and Goddesses (group)	20½" × 17" × 8"	
7	Siva linga	15" × 12" × 6"	
8	Vishnu	27" × 19½" × 11"	
9	Head of Siva	20" × 11" × 9½"	
10	Kirtimukha or griffin	20" × 16" × 11"	
11	Mouth of crocodile	20" × 15" × 7"	
12	Fragment of lion	18" × 13½" × 7"	
13	Fragment of a sculpture playing on flute	12" × 8½" × 7"	
14	Double head	11" × 10" × 6½"	
15	Torso	9½" × 8" × 5"	
16	Piece of a door frame	12" × 9" × 5"	
17	Torso	9" × 8" × 4½"	
18	Bust of woman	9" × 6" × 4"	
19	Torso of woman	8" × 5" × 3½"	
20	Head (human)	9" × 7½" × 6"	
21	Fragment of elephant	8½" × 7" × 6½"	
22	Head of a Jaina image	7" × 5" × 3½"	
23	Piece of a female figure	7" × 6" × 2½"	
24	A torso	4½" × 4½" × 3"	
25	Human hand	6½" × 5" × 3"	
26	Torso of Vishnu	31" × 13½" × 8"	
27	Round pedestal of a pilaster	23" × 13"	
28	Amalasila	14" × 5½"	
29	Amalasila (ceiling slab)	6' × 1'11" × 10"	
30	Fragment of human figure	6" × 4" × 1½"	

Appendix I.

List of Photo Negatives prepared during the Year 1940-41, Samvat 1997.

Serial No.	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
District Bhilsa.				
1	Badher	Loose images near the ruins of a Siva temple ..	Half	
2	"	" " " "	"	
3	"	" " " "	"	
4	"	A big ceiling slab of an old temple with a lotus flower carved on it, locally known as Singar Sila.	"	
5	"	Two stone sculptures Brahma and Vishnu half buried in earth.	Full	
6	"	Two stone sculptures Brahma and Vishnu half buried in earth, another position.	"	
7	Besnagar	Kham-Baba after being reset plumb, view from S. E.	"	
8	"	Kham-Baba after being reset plumb, view from S. W.	"	
9	Bhilsa	Bija mandal mosque, panoramic view, first half.	"	
10	"	" " " " second half.	"	
11	"	Images of Sesha Sayi Vishnu in the open compound of the Dak Bungalow.	"	
12	Gyaraspur.	Atha-khambha after conservation G. V. ..	"	
13	"	" " " " near view from N. E.	"	
14	"	" " " " side " " S. E...	"	
15	"	Bajra Matha temple, after conservation, view from N. W.	"	
16	"	Bajra Matha temple, after conservation, view from S. E.	"	
17	"	Hindola torana, after conservation, view from S. E.	"	
18	"	" " " " " " S. W.	"	
19	"	Chau-khambha near Hindola torana, after conservation, with open air Museum.	"	
20	"	Open air Museum near Chau Khambha, after conservation.	"	
21	"	Maladevi temple, after conservation, G. V. ..	"	
22	"	" " " " partial side view showing basement " and porch from South Pt. I.	"	
23	"	" " " " " " Pt. II. Balcony and basement.	"	

Appendix I.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
24	Gyaraspur.	Maladevi temple, part III showing another balcony and basement, after conservation.	Full.	
25	"	Stupa on Dhenkinath hill, G. V.	"	
26	"	" " " " " " near view from S. after jungle clearance.	"	
27	"	Stupa on Dhenkinath, another near view from N. ..	"	
28	Udaygiri	A huge stone trough on hill	"	
District Gird.				
29	Barai	A triple Jain temple in ruins	Full.	
30	"	Another ruined Jain temple near No. 29, sheltering a huge Jain image.	"	
31	"	Fourfold Jain temple, Pt. I (first two) panoramic view.	"	
32	"	" " " Pt II (last two) " "	"	
33	Gwalior.	Gujari Mahal showing new coping on the compound wall of courtyard from S. W.	"	
34	"	" " showing terrace floor in the western portion after repairs, from S.	"	
35	"	" " " from North, part I. ..	"	
36	"	" " " " " part II.	"	
37	"	" " a building on the North, after partial clearance of debris from N. E.	Half.	
38	"	" " " " " N. W ..	"	
39	"	" " " " " South ..	"	
Archæological Museum.				
40	"	" " " a stone torso	"	
40a	"	" " " " " head	"	
41	"	" " " copy of an old painting of a Rajput King (warrior) on horse back	"	
42	"	" " " copy of Bagh fresco painting, scene of sorrow.	"	
43	"	" " " copy of Bagh fresco painting, music in the air.	"	
44	"	" " " dance (first half)	"	
45	"	" " " " (second ")	"	
46	"	" " " horse procession	"	

Appendix I. (contd.)

	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
47	Gwalior.	" " " elephant "	Full	
		Excavations.		
48	Pawaya	Tila: platform No. 1, during excavation, panoramic view, from S. E. first half.	"	
49	"	Tila: platform No. 1, during excavation, panoramic view, from S. E. second half.	"	
50	"	" platform No. 1, during excavation, view from S. W. first half.	"	
51	"	" " " second half	"	
52	"	Tila: platform No. 1 during excavation, view from S. W. first half.	"	
53	"	Tila: platform No. 1, during excavation, view from S. W. second half.	"	
54	"	" G. V. from N. W.	"	
55	"	" panoramic view from N. E. first half ..	"	
56	"	" " " " second half ..	"	
57	"	" showing bottom and foundations of masonry at S. E. corner.	"	
58	"	Tila platform No. 2 during excavation: panoramic view from S. E. first half.	"	
59	"	" " " " " second "	"	
60	"	" " " " " N. W. first half.	"	
61	"	" " " " " second "	"	
62	"	" " " " " N. E. first half	"	
63	"	" " " " " second "	"	
64	"	Tila, a room in platform No. 1, on N. E. corner ..	"	
65	"	" " " " S. E. " ..	"	
66	"	" platform No. 1 during excavations, view showing holes in masonry in the hearting on east side.	"	
67	"	" " No. 2, during excavations, showing panels in east face.	"	
68	"	" " " " another view ..	"	
69	"	" " No. 2. during excavations, part of south face, upper part.	"	
70	"	" " " " " lower "	"	
71	"	" " another view, upper part ..	"	

Appendix I. (contd.)

Serial No.	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
72	"	Tila, platform No. 2, during excavations, south face, another view lower part.	"	
73	"	Tila, platform No 1 & 2 during excavations, view showing mutual relation in a section in the south face.	"	
74	"	" " " " another view ..	"	
75	"	" " " " still " " ..	"	
76	"	" " " " " " " " ..	"	
77	"	Tila, platform No. 2, view showing traces of plaster on masonry in the west face.	"	
78	"	" " " view showing <i>gola</i> and panels on the north face.	"	
79	"	" " " " another view.	"	
80	"	" " " showing a <i>ghata</i> ornament in a panel in the east face.	"	
81	"	" " " remains of a later room with patches of plaster on wall at N. E. corner.	"	
82	"	" " 3, view showing two later ovens at the North East corner.	"	
83	"	" " " during excavations, view from N. W.	"	
84	"	" " " " " North.	"	
85	"	" " " " " N. E.	"	
86	"	" " " traces of steps in the south face.	"	
87	"	" " " rectangular pits in the masonry near the east face.	"	
88	"	" " " North face ..	"	
89	"	" 2, holes of drains in the hearting of the east face.	Half	
90	"	" 1, a <i>makara</i> spout in mouth of a drain in the east face.	"	
91	"	" " " showing specimen of brick masonry.	"	
92	"	" 2, " " " "	"	
Antiquities found in Excavations.				
93	"	Terra cotta, Brahma seated on lotus	"	

Appendix I. (contd.)

Serial No.	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
94	Pawaya.	Terra cotta, lower portion of goddess Parvati (?) seated on lion.	Half	
95	"	" " bust of woman ..	Full	
96	"	" " " another view ..	"	
97	"	" " human head with big curls of hair and an ornament round neck.	Half	
98	"	" " " another position.	"	
99	"	" " human head with mustache and a crown.	"	
100	"	" " " another view ..	"	
101	"	" " " front view ..	"	
102	"	" " human head with wig of hair ..	Half	
103	"	" " another " " " "	"	
104	"	" " human head smiling ..	"	
105	"	" " " with curls of hair ..	"	
106	"	" " " wigs of hair ..	"	
107	"	" " " weeping ..	"	
108	"	" " human bust ..	"	
109	"	" " group of smiling faces ..	Full	
110	"	" " " weeping " ..	"	
111	"	" " a group of human heads wearing wigs ..	"	
112	"	" " (a) a group of human heads with curls of hair.	"	
		" " (b) " " " weeping faces.	"	
113	"	" " a group of human heads having ear-rings ..	"	
114	"	" " " " " curls of hair ..	"	
115	"	" " miscellaneous human heads ..	"	
116	"	" " human heads with matted hair ..	Half	
117	"	" " miscellaneous human heads ..	"	
118	"	" " " " " " ..	"	
119	"	" " " " " " ..	"	

Appendix I. (contd.)

Serial No.	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
120	Pawaya.	Terra cotta: waist of a torso, and a head with mustache and matted hair.	"	
121	"	" " human busts without heads	Full	
122	"	" " torsos showing dresses of spotted cloth ..	"	
123	"	" " " " " " " " " " " "	Half	
124	"	" " human torsos, upper portions	Full	
125	"	" " " " lower "	"	
126	"	" " " " " " " "	"	
127	"	" " " " " " " "	"	
128	"	" " " " thighs and legs	"	
129	"	" " " " arms	Half	
130	"	" " " " hands	Full	
131	"	" " " " feet	"	
132	"	" " two horses	"	
133	"	" " fragments of figures of animals ..	"	
134	"	" " " " birds	"	
135	"	" " fragments of figures of fish	Half	
136	"	" " pottery	"	
137	"	" " (a) two pieces of bangles ..	"	
		" " (b) branch of a tree	"	
138	"	" " bricks with various finger marks..	Full	
139	"	View of entire bricks showing thickness.. ..	"	
140	"	Two bricks showing length and breadth ..	Half	
141	"	Another group of two bricks showing length and breadth.	"	
142	"	A third group of two bricks showing length and breadth.	"	
143	"	Some carved bricks	Full	
144	"	" " " " " " " " " " " "	"	
145	"	A piece of an inscribed brick	Half	
146	"	A group of stone objects	Full	
147	"	Stone sculptures of a Naga king (?) and Vishnu ..	"	

Appendix I. (contd.)

Serial No.	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
148	Pawaya.	Stone human heads	Half	
149	"	Stone human limbs	"	
150	"	Two stone carved pieces, one stone head of a bear, and a stone foot of an elephant.	"	
151	"	Three carved stone pieces and an inscribed stone piece.	"	
152	"	A carved lid stone in two positions	"	
153	"	Confluence of the Sindh and Parvati rivers, panoramic view, first half.	Full	
154	"	Confluence of the Sindh and Parvati rivers, panoramic view, second half.	"	
District Ujjain.				
Collection of sculptures at the Mahakal temple.				
155	Ujjain	Torso of a god (a stone sculpture.)	Half	
156	"	Some stone images and fragments	Full	
157-58	"	" " " "	"	
159	"	A piece of carved ceiling slab,	"	
160	"	An <i>amalasila</i> and a round <i>chowki</i>	Half	
Treasure-Trove Gold found in Improvement Operations in the City.				
161	"	Thirty-four chips of gold	Full	
162	"	Six gold ornaments with a copper box which contained the treasure.	"	
163	"	Six gold ornaments with a copper box which contained the treasure, another view.	"	
164	"	Six gold ornaments with a copper box which contained the treasure, still another view.	"	
165	"	Twenty-four gold <i>Mohars</i> (obverse)	"	
166	"	" " " " " " " "	"	
167	"	" " " " (reverse)	"	
168	"	" " " " (")	"	
169	"	Observatory: partial view	"	
170	"	" Samrat yantra	"	
171	"	" Digamsa yantra	"	

Appendix I.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks
172	Ujjain	Observatory, Digamsa yantra, another view ..	Full	
173	"	" Sanku yantra	"	
174	"	" Nadivalaya yantra	"	
175	"	" " " another position ..	"	
176	"	" Dakshinavritti yantra	"	
Excavations at Garh				
177	"	Garh, Trench No. 5, view from West ..	"	
178	"	" " " " " East ..	"	
179	"	" " " " " North ..	"	
180	"	" " " later view from North ..	"	
181	"	" " " brick wall of east face, exposed in excavations.	"	
182	"	" " " west face of brick wall excavated.	"	
183	"	" " " 12, upper part, view from N. E.	"	
184	"	" " " lower part, " " "	"	
185	"	" " " upper part, view from S. E.	"	
186	"	" " " an earthen pot exposed in excavations	"	
187	"	" " " an earthen ring exposed in excavations.	"	
188	"	" " " 13, upper part, view from N. E.	"	
189	"	" " " lower part, " " "	"	
190	"	" " " upper part view from South East.	"	
191	"	" " " 14, upper part, " " N. W.	"	
192	"	" " " lower " " " "	"	
193	"	" " " upper " " " S. E.	"	
194	"	" " " No. 14, showing detail of eastern wall	"	
195	"	" " " brick wall in the north side, exposed in excavations.	"	
196	"	" " " showing place of an earthen pot in a wall exposed in excavations.	"	
197	"	" Movable antiquities: lower portion of a big earthen pot found in excavations.	Half	

Appendix I.—(contd)

Serial No.	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Rem rks.
198	Ujjain	Garh, movable antiquities, earthen stands	"	
199	"	" " " " lids, basin, bowls	"	
200	"	" " " " pipe, spout and bowls.	"	
201	"	" " " " pots of various shapes	"	
202	"	" " " " cups and saucers	"	
203	"	" " " " necks and bottoms of vessels	"	
204	"	" " " " vessels with spouts and a jug.	"	
205	"	" " " " incense burners and lamps	"	
206	"	" " " " pinnacles and a chessman.	"	
207	"	" " " " earthen necks of jugs (?)	"	
208	"	" " " " scrubbing brushes, piece of channel, bottoms of saucers (?) and tiles.	"	
209	"	" " " " terra cotta toy figures of animals and a toy wheel.	"	
210	"	" " " " terra cotta human busts, heads, torsos and feet.	"	
211	"	" " " " human busts and heads.	"	
212	"	" " " " weights, <i>damaru</i> , a medal and a pendant.	"	
213	"	" " " " a potter's tool, two pots and an unidentified object.	"	
214	"	" " " " brick with a socket hole for holding the pivot of door and a piece of a decorated vessel.	"	

Appendix I. (concl'd.)

Serial No.	Place.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
215	Ujjain.	Garh movable antiquities „ pieces of polished pottery.	„	
216	„	„ „ „ „ beads	„	
217	„	„ „ „ „ earthen beads, another view.	„	
218	„	„ „ „ „ stone figures, a mould and a piece of decorated vessel.	„	
219	„	„ „ „ „ stone objects	Full.	
220	„	„ „ „ „ stone objects	Half.	
221	„	„ „ „ „ „ balls, crucible-like flint and a bangle.	„	
222	„	„ „ „ „ highly polished cylindrical objects (weights ?)	„	
223	„	„ „ „ „ a polished stone bead and a necklace of beads (?)	„	
224	„	„ „ „ „ shell bangles	„	
225	„	„ „ „ „ carved shell bangles	„	
226	„	„ „ „ „ shell ear-rings, pieces of conch and shell.	„	
227	„	„ „ „ „ bone objects, pieces of a carved hand e of a <i>chowri</i> (?) piece of a bangle and pencils.	„	
228	„	„ „ „ „ metal objects iron ring, nails, pieces of vessel, sickle, knife, a padlock, and two copper sticks.	„	
229	„	„ „ „ „ pieces of mud plaster from bamboo structure.	„	
230	„	„ „ „ „ Miscellaneous - terra cotta figures, heads, and seals, purchased from outside for Archæological Museum, Gwalior.	„	

Appendix K.

List of drawings prepared during the Year 1940-41, Samvat 1997.

S.No.	Place.	Object and description.	Scale.	Remarks.
District Gird.				
1	Pawaya Tila .. (excavations)	Site plan ..	1" = 24'	Nos. 1 to 6 are plotted in pencil only. Incomplete.
2	" ..	Ground plan showing all the three platforms.	1" = 8'	
		(A) SE corner (enlarged plan) ..	} 1" = 1'	
		(B) section on A B. ..		
		(C) section on C D. ..		
3	" ..	East elevation of platforms. ..	1" = 4'	
4	" ..	East elevation of platforms Nos. 2 and 3, with section of platform No. 1.	1" = 4'	
5	" ..	Part of elevation of 2nd platform showing detail.	1" = 1'	
6	" ..	Part of elevation of 3rd platform showing detail.	..	
District Ujjain.				
7	Ujjain Garh .. (excavations)	Plan and elevation of trench No. 12.	} 1" = 5'	Sketch only.
		" " " 13.		
		" " " 14.		
8	" ..	Plan and elevation of trench No. 5.	1" = 5'	Do.

Appendix L.

List of books added to the Office Library, during the Year 1940-41 Samvat 1997.

S. No.	Name of book.	Remarks.
Archæological Survey Reports, Memoirs, etc.		
1	Archæology in Travancore by R. Vasudeo Poduval ..	Exchange.
2	Hindu America by Chamanlal	Purchased.
3	Excavations at Harappa Vol. I, by M. S. Vats..	Exchange.
4	Excavations at Harappa Vol. II, by M. S. Vats ..	"
5	Report of the Superintendent Archæological Survey, Burma, (1939-40).	"
6	The story of the Archæological Department, Hyderabad-Deccan (1914-1939).	"
7	Annual Report of the Archæological Survey of India (1936-37).	"
8	The Archæology in Gujrat (including Kathiawad) ..	Purchased.
9	Archæological Survey of Mysore, Annual Report (1938) ..	Exchange.
10	Archæological Survey of Mysore, Annual Report (1939) ..	"
Art and Architecture.		
11	Indian Art and Letters Vol. XIV, Part I	Gratis.
12	Rupawali by Nandlal Bose	Purchased.
13	The Court Painters of the Grand Mughals by T. W. Arnold and Laurence Binyon.	"
14	The Portfolio of Indian Art by Dr. Coomarswamy ..	"
Bibliography and Catalogues.		
15	Catalogue of the European pictures in the Baroda Museum and Picture Gallery.	Exchange.
16	Catalogue of Manuscripts preserved in the Oriental Manuscripts Library, Ujjain, Part II.	Gratis.
17	Consolidated Catalogue of the Central Archæological Library by Dr. Sharma.	"
Epigraphy.		
18-22	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XXV Parts 3 to 7	"
23	Epigraphia Indica, Vol XXXIII. Part 8	"
24	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XXVI, Part 1	"
25	Descriptive notes on the inscriptions deposited in the Central Museum, Nagpur.	Exchange.
26	Annual Report of South Indian Epigraphy 1940 ..	Gratis.

Appendix L.—(contd.).

S. No.	Name of book.	Remarks.
27	Bombay-Karnatak Inscriptions Vol. V. Part I ..	Gratis.
Geography.		
28	Geographical Essays Vol. I. by B. C. Law	Purchased.
29	Records of the Geological Society of India Vol. LXXV Professional paper No. 1 by A. L. Coulson.	Gratis.
30	Records of the Geological Society of India, Vol. LXXV Professional paper No. 8 by Krishan Ghosh.	"
Guides.		
31	Descriptive Guide to the Baroda Museum and Picture Gallery by S. Ganguli.	Exchange.
32	General Guide to the State Museum and Picture Gallery Baroda by Hiranand Sastri.	"
33	A Short Guide book to the Archaeological Section of the Provincial Museum, Lucknow by Vasudeva Agrawal.	"
34	Gwalior Today by Publicity Department, Gwalior State ..	Purchased.
History.		
35	Ancient India Vol. III by T. L. Shah	"
36	History of Bikaner, Vol. V., Part II by G. S. Ojha ..	"
37	खगोल ज्ञानियों का संक्षिप्त इतिहास by B. L. Thakur	Gratis.
38	A third Journey of exploration in Central Asia by Sir Aurel Stein.	Purchased.
39	The Indo-Iranian Borderlands, their prehistory in the light of Geography and of recent explorations by Sir A. Stein.	"
40	A Historic review of Hindu India (300 B. C. to 1,700 A. D.) by Panchanana Raya.	"
41	Pre-Buddhist India by Ratanlal Mehta	"
Iconography.		
42	Jain Iconography by Prof. Bhattacharya	"
Journals and Periodicals.		
43-54	Modern Review from July 1940 to June 1941 ..	Subscribed.
55-57	Journal of Indian History, Vol. XIX, Parts 1, 2 and 3 ..	"
58	Journal of Indian History, Special Number, 1941 ..	"
59-62	Journal of the Rajwade Samshodhak Mandal, Vol. IX, Parts 2, 3 and 4 and of Vol. X, Part I.	Exchange.
63-66	Quarterly Journal of the Bharat Itihas Samshodhak Mandal, Vol. XXI, Parts 1, 2, 3 and 4.	Subscribed.

Appendix L.—(contd.)

S. No.	Name, of book.	Remarks.
67	Quarterly Journal of the Mythic Society, Vol. XXXI, No. 2.	Gratis.
68	Journal of the University of Bombay, Vol. IX, Part I ..	Exchange.
69-70	Quarterly Journal of the Greater India Society, Vol. VII, Part 2 and Vol. VIII, Part I.	Subscribed.
71-73	Indian Historical Quarterly, Vol. XVI, Parts 2 and 3 and Vol. XVII, Part 1.	"
74	Quarterly Journal of the Punjab Oriental Research, Vol. I, Part 1.	Gratis.
75-76	Indian Culture, Vol. VII, Parts 1 and 2	Subscribed.
77-80	Nagari Pracharini Patrika, Vol. VL, Nos 1, 2, 3 and 4 ..	"
81	Ancient India (Journal of the Narmada Valley Research Society, Vol. I, Part I.	Gratis.
82-83	Annals of Sri Vyankateshwar Oriental Research Institute, Vol. I, Parts 3 and 4.	Exchange.
84	Muslim University Journal for 1940	"
85-86	New Asia, Vol. II, Parts 3 and 4	"
87	Karnatak Historical Review, Vol. V, Part 2	"
88	Journal of the Numismatic Society of India, Vol. II ..	"
89-90	Annals of the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute, Vol. XXI, Parts 1 and 2.	Presented.
91	Journal of the Andhra Historical Research Society, Vol. XIII, Part 1.	Exchange.
92	Journal of the Aligarh Historical Research Society for 1941.	"
93	New Indian Antiquary, Vol. III, Part 12	"
94-95	Oriental Literary Digest, Vol. III, Nos. 11 and 12 ..	"
Literature.		
96	नारायणपुरी कृत हनीरकाव्य, लेखक एन. जे. कीर्तने	Purchased.
97	Bhasa—a study by A. D. Pusalkar	"
98	प्रबन्धचिन्तामणि by Merutungacharya edited by Jinavijayasuri ..	"
99	अलंकारमञ्जूषा by Bhatta Devishankara Purohita	"
Museum.		
100	A brief description of the Museum and Picture Gallery, Baroda by A. G. Widgery.	Exchange.
101	A Travelling Report of the Museum and Picture Gallery, Baroda by Dr. Ernst Cohn Wisner.	"

Appendix L.—(concl'd.).

S. No.	Name of book.	Remarks.
102	Annual Report of the Watson Museum of Antiquities, Rajkot, for 1940.	Exchange.
103	Annual Report of the Curzon Museum, Muttra for 1940 ..	"
104	Annual Report of the Government Museum, Travancore, for 1940.	"
105	Report on the working of the State Museum, Podukkottai, 1939-40.	"
106	Report of the Prince of Wales Museum of Western India, 1939-40.	"
107	Annual Report of the Provincial Museum, Lucknow, 1940-41	"
Miscellaneous.		
108	Tirupati and its environs (A publication of the All India Oriental Conference, X Session 1940).	"
109	A plea for reorientation of Oriental thought by B. L. Atre ..	"
110	Speeches of Maharaja Scindia in 1937	"
111	History of Hindu Mathematics by Dutta and Narayan Singh.	Purchased.
112	Concepts of Buddhism by Dr. B. C. Law	"
113	Dr. Bhandarkar volume 1940 by Dr. B. C. Law ..	"
114	The Buddhist conception of Spirits by Dr. B. C. Law ..	"
115	Mahavira, his life and teaching by Dr. B. C. Law ..	"
116	Aryan trail in Iran and India by Nagenda Nath Ghosh ..	"
117	Jha Commemoration volume	Gratis.
118	शिवाजीचा राजनीति by भास्कर वामन भट	"
Numismatics.		
119	Proceedings of the Numismatic Society of India, 1940 ..	"
State Publications.		
120	Commercial Directory of the Gwalior State, 1934 ..	"
121	General Statistics of the Gwalior State, for Samvat 1993 ..	"
122	Administration Report of the Gwalior state for Samvat, 1936-37.	"

Appendix M.

Statement of Expenditure incurred during the Year 1940-41, Samvat 1997.

S.No.	Head.	Amount Spent.			Total.	Remarks.	
		Current year.		Last year.			
		Rs.	a.	p.	Rs.	a.	p.
	I Recurring.						
1	Salaries	13,628	11	9			
2	Travelling Allowances	2,134	15	9			
3	Contingencies	1,114	14	11	10	4	0
4	Publications	838	2	3			
5	Office Library (Books)	394	5	7	34	12	0
6	Archæological Museum	1,201	14	11	138	4	0
	(a) Collection and purchase of antiquities	376	7	0			
	(b) Exhibition of antiquities	725	8	6			
	(c) Upkeep of Museum building	99	15	5			
	Total	1,201	14	11			
7	Miscellaneous						
8	Works	3,025	11	3	227	10	5
9	Telephone subscription	125	0	0			
10	Cycle Allowances	14	9	9			
11	Works from general saving	717	6	11			
	Total Recurring Grant	23,195	13	1	410	14	5
	II. Non-recurring.						
1	Special repairs to Bagh Caves	9,091	15	9	606	4	0
2	Archæological Museum (Building improvement and furniture).	1,212	1	0			
3	Archæological excavations	804	11	5	3,693	14	7
4	Caretaker hut at Suhania				198	4	1
5	Rest house at Gyaspur				94	0	0
6	Purchase of Bagh Caves wall paintings for Archæological Museum from Mr. Katchadaurian.				718	5	0
7	Conservation of monuments at Terahi and Kadwaha.				811	1	0
8	Repairs to a well near the Kakanmadh temple at Suhania.				829	3	11
	Total Non-recurring	11,108	12	2	6,951	0	10
	Grand Total	34,304	9	3	7,361	15	3

Appendix N.

Statement of Income realised during the Year 1940-41, Samvat 1997.

S.No.	Item.	Amount.	Remarks.
1	2	3	4
		Rs. a. p.	
1	By sale of publications	75 12 10	
2	„ „ photographs	143 15 0	
3	„ „ coins	104 12 0	
4	Miscellaneous	50 8 0	
	Total	374 15 10	

Excavations at Ujjain : Garh site : pottery.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(f)

(e)

(g)

Excavations at Ujjain : Garh site : portable antiquities.

(a) Terra cotta human figurines.

(d) Terra cotta toy figurines of animals.

(b) Stone figurines, and a die of an ear ring.

(c) Stone and shell beads.

(e) Miscellaneous earthen objects.

Excavations at Padmavati (Pawaya) : Tila site.

(a) Excavated platforms G, V. from N. W.

(b) North face of platform No. 2.

(c) Platform No. 2. Detail of decoration on North face.

Excavations at Padmavati (Pawaya) : Tila site :
terra cotta human heads and a bust.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

Excavations at Padmavati (Pawayā) : Tila site.

(a) Terra cotta heads with smiling faces.

(b) Terra cotta heads with weeping faces.

Excavations at Padmavati (Pawaya) : Tila site :
terra cotta figures.

(a) Brahman.

(b) Bust of a woman.

(c) Lower portion of a goddess (Parvati ?) on lion.

Excavations at Padmavati (Pawaya) : Tila site.

(a) Terra cotta figure of a horse.

(b) Terra cotta figures of birds and fish.

(c) Fragment of a brick inscribed in Gupta characters.

(d) A stone figure of four-armed Vishnu.

(a) A Bundela Rajput king on horse back
(a painting in the Archaeological Museum at Gwalior)

(b) Gold ornaments found in treasure trove at Ujjain.

Excavations at Padmavati (Pawaya) : Tila site :
fragments of terra cotta human figurines.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Coins

(a) 1-2. Shams-ud-din Altamsh
A.H. 607-633
A.D. 1210-1235

3-4. Muiz-ud-din Bahram Shah
A.H. 637-639
A.D. 1239-1241

(b) 5-6. Ala-ud-din Masud Shah
A.H. 639-644
A.D. 1241-1246

7-8. Nasir-ud-din Mahmud Shah
A.H. 644-664
A.D. 1246-1265

from
J. P. M.
DIRECTOR OF ARCHAEOLOGY,
GWALIOR STATE.

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